

D7.1 – SCENT enhanced datasets for images and text as web services

Smart Toolbox for Engaging Citizens into a People-Centric Observation Web

Abstract

Whilst citizen participation in environmental policy making is still in its infancy, there are signs of a growing level of interest. The majority of citizens, though, both as individuals and as groups often feel disengaged from influencing environmental policies. They also remain unaware of publicly available information, such as the GEOSS or Copernicus initiatives. The SCENT project will alleviate this barrier. It will enable citizens to become the ‘eyes’ of the policy makers by monitoring land-cover/use changes in their everyday activities. This is done through a constellation of smart collaborative technologies delivered by the SCENT toolbox in TRLs 6-8.

This deliverable intends to describe the implementation details of the SCENT Harmonisation platform, one of the key components of the SCENT Toolbox, aiming to integrate semantically annotated data (i.e. metadata of crowd-sourced images of land cover / land use (LC/LU) elements, measurements from portable and in-situ sensors, maps, etc) provided from the different toolbox components and offer them as Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) compliant web services. The Harmonisation platform has been designed to ensure interoperability, discoverability and re-usability of the citizen-science data collected in the context of the project while facilitating their integration and utilisation with in-situ data sources. Resources that have been harmonized and exposed from the platform are offered to GEOSS so as to enable their further exploitation from the global community.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LC/LU	Land Cover/ Land Use
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
REST	Representational State Transfer
SOS	Sensor Observation Service
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
CSV	Comma-separated Values file
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
JAR	Java Archive
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
JWT	JSON Web Token
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
GUI	Graphical User Interface
SPA	Single-page Application
DAB	Discovery and Access Broker
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Table 1: List of Abbreviations

Executive Summary

The deliverable aims to provide an overview of the technical implementation of SCENT Harmonisation platform as well as of activities undertaken to ensure interoperability of citizen-science data and their connection to GEOSS platform and other relevant national repositories.

SCENT Harmonisation Platform enables the management, storage and provision of all citizen-generated data, in-situ measurements and added-value information produced by the various SCENT tools (i.e. improved Land Cover / Land Use maps, flood pattern determination maps) and translates them to standardised resources following the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards. In addition, the Harmonisation Platform ensures correctness/accuracy of the user measurements, user reliability and protection of the system from malicious contributions.

The document is initiated with an overview of the platform architecture whilst subsequently deepening on the dedicated components details and the process to connect to GEOSS. To support relevant initiatives, projects and users to overcome challenges in the aspects tackled by the Harmonisation Platform as well as to shape the way forward in the field of citizen science data interoperability relevant recommendations are also provided.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The deliverable constitutes a technical report aiming to describe the implementation aspects and functionalities of the SCENT Harmonisation Platform

1.2 Intended readership

This deliverable is public and can therefore be accessed by anyone with an interest in it. More specifically the document can be utilised as a useful guide showcasing functional and technical considerations and approaches towards managing the ample of resources that can be produced in the context of a Citizen Observatory, ensuring interoperability and combined utilisation of citizen-science data with other data sources and applications and facilitating the connection of diverse environmental information to GEOSS and other national repositories.

1.3 Relationship with other SCENT deliverables

The starting point for this deliverable is D1.4 (“SCENT toolbox system architecture definition”) that defines the high-level SCENT toolbox system architecture deployed in the pilots. The deliverable complies also with the relevant procedures described in D8.3 Data Management and POPD Requirements (mid-term review update) and D9.3 Ethical Issues Clearance Plan.

1.4 Document’s structure

Being a technical report, the document is organized in 9 main chapters. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the scope and objectives of the SCENT Harmonisation Platform while also describes its requirements and the implemented architecture. Chapter 3 describes data interoperability considerations and standards that have been used and implemented, while chapters 4-8 present the functionalities and the implementation details of the main components of the Harmonisation Platform including the persistence storage, data translators, data quality module, data provision and visualisation site. Chapter 9 provide details about the process towards offering SCENT resources to GEOSS Platform and the certification of OGC compliant services exposed by the Harmonisation Platform. Last but not least, Chapter 10 complements the abovementioned analysis with the conclusions as well as with a summary of recommendations related to future implementations.

2 Overview of the SCENT Harmonisation platform

2.1 Introduction

The SCENT Harmonisation platform is tasked with the data collection, quality control, storage and management of all the data collected or created by all the SCENT components. The Harmonisation platform is also responsible for the data interoperability, the translation of the collected data to OGC compliant observations and the provision of this information either visualized to people interested in exploring it or through proper APIs following OGC standards.

The data collected at the Harmonisation platform include:

- Image metadata, containing annotations regarding LC/LU elements, pre-defined categories of event reports or water level information as extracted by the Water Level Measurement Tool;
- Video metadata, including water velocity information as extracted by the Water Velocity Calculation Tool;
- Crowd-sourced environmental measurements, air temperature and soil moisture, collected by the portable sensors by volunteers;
- In-situ water level measurements from available infrastructure;
- Flood models and time series data as extracted by the simulations;
- Orthomosaics and digital elevation models, collected during targeted drone flights in areas of high hydrological interest;
- Land cover / land use maps as produced by the Map Segmentation tool.

The collected data are stored in a persistent storage as OGC compliant observations and made available through the appropriate APIs that ensure the availability of the information to multiple users at the same time.

2.2 Requirements

The requirements for the Harmonisation platform have been identified in the Deliverable 1.3, SCENT toolbox system requirements. The platform is responsible for consolidating data and adding it to GEOSS and national repositories as OGC-based observations. We present here a summary of the requirements as well as the component of the platform architecture that is responsible for fulfilling it.

Table 2 Requirements for the Harmonisation platform

Requirement	Description	Priority	Component
SYS_NF_HARM_1	The harmonisation platform collects semantically annotated data from the SIE and the Crowdsourcing platform and translates them into OGC compliant resources.	MUST	Data translators
SYS_NF_HARM_2	The harmonisation platform publishes OGC compliant resources to the GEOSS platform	MUST	GEOSS Portal page dedicated to SCENT

SYS_NF_HARM_3	The harmonisation platform hosts a web server supporting OGC compliant standards for GEOSS service invocation.	SHOULD	Dedicated SCENT GeoServer
SYS_NF_HARM_4	Industry standard network security mechanisms protect the harmonisation platform.	MUST	Multiple Security mechanisms
SYS_NF_HARM_5	The harmonisation platform scales and performs sufficiently for a large amount of end users such as Alex, Julia, Lucas and Laura.	MUST	Distributed Database Layer

2.3 Architecture

As discussed above, the Harmonisation platform receives data from many heterogeneous sources aiming to harmonize these sources and provide the data in a unified way. A detailed architectural diagram of the Harmonisation platform is available in Figure 1.

The data sources can be divided in three main categories based on the way they are produced and arrive at the platform, these are:

- Raster data. These data are data collected from the drones, orthomosaic and DEM, time series produced by the flood models and raster data with the output of the flood model simulations and the map segmentation simulations. These data are produced sporadically, once or twice during the course of the project, are never updated and are of high volume in the order of hundreds of Gigabytes. To facilitate the exchange of these data, the components producing them, make them available to the Harmonisation platform through a dedicated cloud server.
- Crowd-sourced data. These data are collected by volunteers during the project’s citizen science campaigns. They are produced in great volumes, in short time spans as tens of volunteers simultaneously collect data during the campaign activities. These data arrive at the Harmonisation platform through the CROWD BE, using dedicated MQTT receivers.
- In-situ monitoring systems. These data are collected by in-situ sensors, as described in Deliverable 3.2, they arrive in daily bulks at the sftp server and are then forwarded to the Harmonisation platform.

Upon their arrival, the data pass through dedicated Data translators, as presented in Chapter 5, where they are transformed to OGC compliant observations. Due to the heterogeneity of the data sources they are translated in two standards. Crowd-sourced and in-situ measurements are translated based on the OGC SensorThings API standard. Raster data and crowd-sourced metadata are translated based on the OGC WFS/WMS web services. The architectural design is modular, allowing us the flexibility to adapt to new data sources very easily, by adding the proper data translator.

Next, the data go through the data quality control module. The data quality control includes controls about data models, structure and types, co-ordinates references systems for the raster data, date

and time formats, time zones but also content controls. Given that the LC/LU annotations pass an extensive quality control at the CROWD BE, where additional contributions through the SCENT Collaborate are requested and that raster data are produced by SCENT components that use data that have been through assurance control, the platform focuses on the environmental measurements. Measurements collected by the in-situ and portable sensors go through a data quality control module as described in Chapter 6.

Data translated to the SensorThings API are stored in a Distributed Database schema while data translated to WFS/WMS are stored in a dedicated GeoServer, as described in Chapter 2.

Data stored based on the SensorThings API standard are provisioned through a Java implementation of the SensorThings API as a REST server. Raster data and crowd-sourced metadata are provisioned through a dedicated GeoServer as map overlays and feature stores.

In order to ensure that applications can have harmonized access to the stored information we have developed a Custom API which harmonizes the two standards and provide the information in a uniform way. Both the SCENT Campaign Manager and the SCENT Explore Application utilize this custom API in order to access crowd-sourced data and map overlays.

The stored information is visualized by two modules, one taking advantage the SensorThings API and focusing on exploring its query capabilities, in order to provide interesting visualisations and time series. The other model is based in the WMS/WFS services, offering interactive map visualisations and access to the metadata collected.

Last but not least, the information stored in the WMS/WFS services is made available through the GEOSS portal, while the implementation of the SensorThings API is certified by the OGC.

Figure 1 SCENT Harmonisation Platform Architecture

3 Standards

Standardisation constitutes a key process of the Harmonisation Platform, enabling the maximization of the value of the data provided by the project through the utilisation of common systems for transmitting and/or exchanging environmental information. The following sections present the two standards that have been implemented in the context of the Harmonisation platform, while explaining their scope, applicability and advantages.

3.1 SensorThings API

The SensorThings API¹ is an Open Geospatial Consortium² (OGC) standard providing an open and unified framework to interconnect Internet of Things³ (IoT) sensing devices, data, and applications over the Web. It is an open standard addressing the syntactic interoperability and semantic interoperability of the Internet of Things. It complements the existing IoT networking protocols by addressing the ability for different IoT systems to use and understand the exchanged information. As an OGC standard, SensorThings API also allows easy integration into existing Spatial Data Infrastructures or Geographic Information Systems.

It is designed specifically for resource-constrained IoT devices and the Web developer community. It follows REST principles, the JSON⁴ encoding, and the OASIS OData protocol⁵ and URL conventions. The foundation of the SensorThings API is its data model that is based on the ISO 19156, ISO/OGC Observations and Measurements⁶, that defines a conceptual model for observations, and for features involved in sampling when making observations. In the context of the SensorThings, the features are modelled as Things, Sensors and Feature of Interests. As a result, the SensorThings API provides an interoperable Observation-focus view, that is particularly useful to reconcile the differences between heterogeneous sensing systems. The complete data model of the standard is available in Figure 2.

The data model has eight different entities each representing specific information needed for the modeling of sensor measurements. These entities are:

- **Thing:** an object of the physical world (physical things) or the information world (virtual things) that is capable of being identified and integrated into communication networks.
- **Location:** locates the Thing or the Things it associated with. A Thing's Location entity is defined as the last known location of the Thing. A Thing's Location may be identical to the Thing's Observations' FeatureOfInterest. In the context of the IoT, the principle location of interest is usually associated with the location of the Thing, especially for in-situ sensing applications.
- **HistoricalLocation:** provides the times of the current (i.e., last known) and previous locations of the Thing.
- **Datastream:** groups a collection of Observations measuring the same ObservedProperty and produced by the same Sensor.

¹ <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/sensorthings>

² <https://www.opengeospatial.org/>

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_of_things

⁴ <https://www.json.org/>

⁵ https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=odata

⁶ <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/om>

- **Sensor:** an instrument that observes a property or phenomenon with the goal of producing an estimate of the value of the property.
- **ObservedProperty:** specifies the phenomenon of an Observation.
- **Observation:** the act of measuring or otherwise determining the value of a property.
- **FeatureOfInterest:** An Observation results in a value being assigned to a phenomenon. The phenomenon is a property of a feature, the latter being the FeatureOfInterest of the Observation [OGC and ISO 19156:2011]. In the context of the Internet of Things, many Observations' FeatureOfInterest can be the Location of the Thing. In the case of remote sensing, the FeatureOfInterest can be the geographical area or volume that is being sensed.

Figure 2 SensorThings API data model

Mapping the above to a real-world example can begin with any IoT device or system. This is modelled as a Thing. A Thing has a current Location, the last place from where this device send data, and multiple HistoricalLocations, previously known locations from which data were send. Each Thing is associated with one or more Datastreams. Each Datastream groups together values about one ObservedProperty collected by one Sensor. Each Datastream has many Observations from the same triplet of Thing/Sensor/ ObservedProperty. Each Observation recorded by the Sensor observes one particular FeatureOfInterest.

The SensorThings API was chosen for the modeling of both crowd-sourced and in-situ measurements collected in the context of SCENT for two main reasons. Firstly, it allows the efficient modeling of ‘moving sensors’. Portable sensors are used to collect measurements from different areas and pilot sites and are equipped by multiple users. Also, volunteers may use multiple sensors within a campaign to collect measurements. The flexibility of the SensorThings API, that models

independently the sensor, from the volunteer and from the location that the measurement was collected at, is ideal for these types of data and use cases. What is more, the SensorThings API can support heterogeneous measurements collected from the same volunteer using the same sensor. This is very important as a volunteer is using a smart phone to collect information about LC/LU, water level and water velocity and the same portable sensor to collect air temperature and soil moisture.

In addition, the SensorThings API standard has some key advantages over similar standards, such as the OGC Sensor Observation Service (SOS). To begin with, the data format exchange is based on the JSON encoding which is lightweight and easy to create and exchange over the network minimizing the overhead that the XML schema adds to the data objects. Also, the SensorThings API is based on a Resource Oriented Architecture, offering standards and guidelines about the data models and the entities that structure the information. In addition, the standard is based on the REST Web services, meaning that it is stateless and clearly separates the concerns of client and server. Furthermore, the standard supports HTTP POST, DELETE, PUT and PATCH allowing the creation, update and deletion of entities as needed. Last but not least, it allows the retrieval of the information using pagination, ensuring scalability and short response times.

3.2 Web Feature Service / Web Mapping Service

The Open Geospatial Consortium has defined several Open Web Services for accessing geographic data. The two basic service sets are the Web Feature Services⁷(WFS) and the Web Map Services⁸ (WMS). The WFS is concerned with direct access to the underlying data allowing reading, writing, and updating the features, while the WMS is concerned with transforming these features into a map as a static image.

The WMS provides a simple HTTP interface for requesting geo-registered map images from one or more distributed geospatial databases. A WMS request defines the geographic layer and area of interest to be processed. The response to the request is one or more geo-registered map image that can be displayed in a browser application. In addition, WMS allows for uniform rendering access to features stored on a server, and is extremely useful for producing maps, overlays and spatial information as a static image. It offers however little to none querying capabilities.

The WFS represents a change in the way geographic information is created, modified and exchanged on the Internet. Rather than sharing geographic information at the file level the WFS offers direct fine-grained access to geographic information at the feature and feature property level.

With the term feature, we are referring to an Object that is an abstraction of a real-world phenomenon. This object has a set of properties associated with it, each having a name, a type, and a value. Typically, these features are stored in a spatial database or shapefile.

⁷ <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wfs>

⁸ <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wms>

This standard specifies discovery operations, query operations, locking operations, transaction operations and operations to manage stored, parameterized query expressions. Discovery operations allow the service to be interrogated to determine its capabilities and to retrieve the application schema that defines the feature types that the service offers. Query operations allow features or values of feature properties to be retrieved from the underlying data store based upon constraints, defined by the client, on feature properties. Locking operations allow exclusive access to features for the purpose of modifying or deleting features. Transaction operations allow features to be created, changed, replaced and deleted from the underlying data store. Stored query operations allow clients to create, drop, list and described parameterized query expressions that are stored by the server and can be repeatedly invoked using different parameter values.

In the taxonomy of services defined in ISO 19119, the WFS is primarily a feature access service but also includes elements of a feature type service, a coordinate conversion/transformation service and geographic format conversion service.

WFS allows uniform direct access to the features stored on a server. As a result, a WFS is used to provide uniform access to heterogeneous sources, query of these features, spatial support and dynamin manipulation (create, delete, update) over the features.

In the context of SCENT, the WFS/WMS services are crucial for the provision in a uniform manner the collected information as map overlays. The geo-location and the spatial distribution of the collected information is of high importance to scientists and policy makers when analyzing the data.

4 Persistent Storage

4.1 Functionality

The SCENT Harmonisation Platform is tasked to manage ample of data collected in the context of the project's citizen-science activities as well as the ones produced by the various SCENT toolbox components. Thus, the goal is to offer a storage solution that is scalable, stores millions of measurements with different time and spatial distributions, responds to queries efficiently and provides access to multiple users at the same time. To this end, and in order to cover the needs of all the data sources, two different persistent storage schemas have been implemented. The first one, is a distributed database layer that stores the SensorThings API schema while the second is a series of feature stores accessible through a web server (GeoServer).

4.2 Implementation details

4.2.1 Distributed Database Layer

The distributed database layer has been implemented employing a distributed key-value storage schema that uses the GeoMesa⁹ indexing tools over an Accumulo¹⁰ datastore, that uses Apache Hadoop¹¹ and Apache Zookeeper¹² to maintain multiple clusters.

The Apache Hadoop software library is a framework that allows for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers using simple programming models. It is designed to scale up from single servers to thousands of machines, each offering local computation and storage. Further to this, Apache ZooKeeper is a centralized service for maintaining configuration information, naming, providing distributed synchronization, and providing group services. It aims at distilling the essence of these different services into a very simple interface to a centralized coordination service. Building on top of Apache Hadoop and Apache ZooKeeper, Accumulo provides a highly scalable sorted, distributed key-value store, supported by cell-level access labels and server-side programming mechanisms.

GeoMesa is an open source suite of tools that enables large-scale geospatial querying and analytics on distributed computing systems. A Z-ordering index is implemented for the spatial information stored, which supports the efficient indexing of data with diverse spatial distributions as well as multiple measurements from the same spatial location as is the case with the in-situ sensors.

This architectural design allows us to support complex spatio-temporal queries for millions of data elements distributed in multiple clusters.

For the SensorThings API, the tables have been implemented at the Accumulo datastore following the standards data model as shown in Figure 2. The only changes were limited to the addition of a unique entity identifier, allowing us to identify, update and delete specific entities and the addition of the proper links between entities. The implemented storage schema is presented in detail below as tables along with the data type for each field. The mandatory fields of the SensorThings API are highlighted in bold, whilst the additional fields are displayed with blue color.

Table 3 Things data model

EntityId	Integer
Name	String
Description	String
Properties	JSON Object

⁹ <https://www.geomesa.org/>

¹⁰ <https://accumulo.apache.org/>

¹¹ <http://hadoop.apache.org/>

¹² <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

Table 4 Locations data model

EntityId	Integer
Name	String
Description	String
EncodingType	ValueCode
Location	GeoJSON

Table 5 HistoricalLocations data model

EntityId	Integer
Time	Date
ThingEntityId	Integer
LocationEntityId	Integer

Table 6 Datastreams

EntityId	Integer
Name	String
Description	String
UnitOfMeasurement	JSON Object
ObservationType	ValueCode
ObservedArea	GeoJSON
PhenomenonTime	Time interval
ResultTime	Time interval
SensorEntityId	Integer
ObservedPropertyEntityId	Integer
ThingEntityId	Integer

Table 7 Sensors data type

EntityId	Integer
Name	String
Description	String
EncodingType	ValueCode
Metadata	JSON Object

Table 8 ObservedProperties data type

EntityId	Integer
Name	String
Description	String
Definition	URI

Table 9 Observations data types

EntityId	Integer
PhenomenonTime	Time Interval
Result	String
ResultTime	Time Interval
ResultQuality	Integer
ValidTime	Time Interval
Parameters	JSON Object
FeatureOfinterestEntityId	Integer
DatastreamEntityId	Integer

Table 10 FeatureOfInterest data type

EntityId	Integer
Name	String
Description	String
EncodingType	ValueCode
Feature	GeoJSON

Table 11 Association between Things and Locations. (many-to-many relation)

ThingEntityId	Integer
LocationEntityId	Integer

4.2.2 GeoServer & Feature Stores

Data received as raster layers, shape (vector) files and time series information, including the outputs from the flood models map segmentation tools, are stored in the GeoServer data directory and handled by the provided services.

GeoServer is an open source Java-based software server for viewing, editing and sharing geospatial data. It is designed for interoperability; it publishes data from any major spatial data source using open standards, whilst it supports OGC compliant implementations of a number of open standards such as Web Feature Service (WFS), Web Map Service (WMS), and Web Coverage Service (WCS), etc.

For each crowd-sourced metadata, a dedicated GeoMesa feature store is created. Each GeoMesa feature store is integrated to GeoServer, enabling the presentation of a list with its feature types and the creation of a layer of the data. Then the layer is available through the WFS/WMS services along with all the associated functionalities such as data retrieval and querying.

The feature stores created for the metadata are presented below in detail, highlighting the mandatory fields in bold.

Table 12 Image metadata Feature store

ImageId	Integer- Unique image identifier
UserId	Integer-Unique user identifier

Azimuthium	Integer- GPS parameter
Altitude	Integer- GPS parameter
Elevation	Integer- GPS parameter
Accuracy	Double- GPS parameter
SourceType	String- Explore or OpenImageTool
URI	String- Cloud server link to the multimedia
Status	String- Valid or invalid
Description	String- Information added by tools during the image processing
Timestamp	Date- Time of image capture
Position	Point- EPSG:4326
Tags	List- Valid tags associated with the image

Table 13 Video metadata Feature store

Videoid	Integer-Unique video identifier
Userid	Integer-Unique user identifier
Azimuth	Integer- GPS parameter
Altitude	Integer- GPS parameter
Elevation	Integer- GPS parameter
Accuracy	Double- GPS parameter
URI	String- Cloud server link to the multimedia
Status	String- Valid or invalid
Description	String- Information added by tools during the image processing
Timestamp	Date- Time of video capture
Position	Point- EPSG:4326
Confidence	Double- Measurement confidence based on quality
WaterVelocity	Double-Extracted measurement if the video is valid

Table 14 Event report metadata Feature store

EventId	Integer-Unique event identifier
Userid	Integer-Unique user identifier
Azimuth	Integer- GPS parameter
Altitude	Integer- GPS parameter
Elevation	Integer- GPS parameter
Accuracy	Double- GPS parameter
URI	String- Cloud server link to the multimedia
Status	String- Valid or invalid
Timestamp	Date- Time of event reporting
Position	Point- EPSG:4326
EventType	String- As selected by the pre-defined list of event report types

CriticalityLevel	String-Low, medium or high
FreeText	String-Descriptive information as provided by the user submitting the event report

Table 15 Temperature measurement Feature store

TemperatureId	Integer-Unique temperature measurement identifier
UserId	Integer-Unique user identifier
Azimuth	Integer- GPS parameter
Altitude	Integer- GPS parameter
Elevation	Integer- GPS parameter
Accuracy	Double- GPS parameter
Timestamp	Date- Time of measurement collection
Position	Point- EPSG:4326
SensorId	String- Unique sensor identifier
Value	Double- Air Temperature
UnitOfMeasure	String- Celsius or Fahrenheit
TrustLevel	Double- Confidence about the accuracy of the measurement based on the DQC analysis

Table 16 Moisture measurement Feature store

MoistureId	Integer-Unique moisture measurement identifier
UserId	Integer-Unique user identifier
Azimuth	Integer- GPS parameter
Altitude	Integer- GPS parameter
Elevation	Integer- GPS parameter
Accuracy	Double- GPS parameter
Timestamp	Date- Time of measurement collection
Position	Point- EPSG:4326
SensorId	String- Unique sensor identifier
Value	Double- Soil moisture
UnitOfMeasure	String- Percentage
TrustLevel	Double- Confidence about the accuracy of the measurement based on the DQC analysis

5 Data Translators

5.1 Functionality

The Data Translators are the entry points of information for the Harmonisation platform. Each translator receives data from a specific source, translates them to standardised resources and pushes the data to the Data Quality control. The Data translators also ensure that the received data respect the format and types of the data models. They are using the available information in the received data object, trying to transform it based on the requirements of each standard. In case the data received are not complete or the JSON values are not the proper data types, then they discard the data object, properly logging this information. In any other case, they forward the transformed data objects to the quality control module.

5.2 Implementation details

5.2.1 Crowd-sourced metadata and measurements

Each data object as received through the MQTT is being using the appropriate Java scripts. One feature entry is created for the corresponding feature store and the needed entries for the SensorThings API. The feature stores as presented in Chapter 4, have been carefully designed to include the complete information of the received metadata. The translation is mostly focused on eliminating nested information and complex data objects. We presented below examples of the translation of received custom JSON messages to the corresponding feature store.

Table 17 Data Translator for Image feature store

<pre>{ "imageld": 37141, "status": "valid", "statusDesc": "image validated", "takenAt": 1561190121, "source": { "type": "scentUser", "id": 1, "crowdURI": "https://imagecloudstorage.scent-project.eu/kifisos/image/sq3900DA7yicvllT5ONR.jpg"}, "classification": { "explore": { "userId": 667, "objects": [{ "tag": "River bank.Shrubs", "distanceToObject": 10, "status": "valid" }] } } }</pre>	Imageld	37141
	Userld	667
	Azimuthium	0
	Altitude	0
	Elevation	0
	Accuracy	899.9990234375
	SourceType	Explore
	URI	https://imagecloudstorage.scent-project.eu/kifisos/image/sq3900DA7yicvllT5ONR.jpg
	Status	Valid
	Description	image validated

<pre>"SIE": [{ "boundingBox": { "top": 0, "left": 0, "width": 480, "height": 640 }, "objects": [{ "tag": "River bank.Shrubs", "conf": 0.96, "status": "valid" }]}, "pilot": "kifisos", "angCamOrient": { "Az": 0, "Alt": 0}, "geoCamCoor": { "latitude": 37.916053771973, "longitude": 23.714378356934, "elevation": 0, "accuracy": 899.9990234375}}</pre>	Timestamp	22/06/2019 7:55:21 AM
	Position	(37.91605,23.71437)
	Tags	[River bank.Shrubs]

Table 18 Data Translator for Video feature store

<pre>{ "videoid": 2670, "pilot": "kifisos", "geoCamCoor": { "longitude": 23.7248630523682, "latitude": 38.0239715576172 }, "CrowdURI": "https://imagecloudstorage.scnt- project.eu/kifisos/video/DUfYYRDKBt5YcLE1C2mx .mp4", "validation": { "conf": 0.11991010760107512, "isValid": "true" }, "waterVelocity": 0.1413767151817979, "takenAt": 1561282680, "status": "Annotated", "fps": 29.384328358208954, "source": { "id": 652, "type": "scntUser" } }</pre>	Videoid	2670
	Userid	652
	Azimuth	
	Altitude	
	Elevation	
	Accuracy	
	URI	https://imagecloudstorage.scnt-project.eu/kifisos/video/DUfYYRDKBt5YcLE1C2mx.mp4
	Status	Valid
	Description	
	Timestamp	23/06/2019 9:38:00 AM
	Position	(23.72486,38.023971)
	Confidence	0.11991
	WaterVelocity	0.14137

}	
---	--

Table 19 Data Translator for Event report feature store

<pre>{ "criticalityLevel": 1, "takenAt": 1561021182, "gps": { "lat": 37.9175453186035, "lon": 23.717357635498 }, "userId": 2, "reportType": "Blocked.River", "freeText": "", "id": "mgSzplBQlec8TW5wk3IO", "status": "valid", "CrowdURI": "https://imagecloudstorage.scen- project.eu/kifisos/image/VmXCxZ88Sofox4AoUtl6.jpg" }</pre>	<table border="1"> <tr><td>EventId</td><td>mgSzplBQlec8TW5wk3IO</td></tr> <tr><td>UserId</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>Azimuth</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Altitude</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Elevation</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Accuracy</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>URI</td><td>https://imagecloudstorage.scen-project.eu/kifisos/image/VmXCxZ88Sofox4AoUtl6.jpg</td></tr> <tr><td>Status</td><td>Valid</td></tr> <tr><td>Timestamp</td><td>20/06/2019 8:59:42 AM</td></tr> <tr><td>Position</td><td>(37.91754,23.71735)</td></tr> <tr><td>EventType</td><td>Blocked.River</td></tr> <tr><td>CriticalityLevel</td><td>Low</td></tr> <tr><td>FreeText</td><td></td></tr> </table>	EventId	mgSzplBQlec8TW5wk3IO	UserId	2	Azimuth		Altitude		Elevation		Accuracy		URI	https://imagecloudstorage.scen-project.eu/kifisos/image/VmXCxZ88Sofox4AoUtl6.jpg	Status	Valid	Timestamp	20/06/2019 8:59:42 AM	Position	(37.91754,23.71735)	EventType	Blocked.River	CriticalityLevel	Low	FreeText	
EventId	mgSzplBQlec8TW5wk3IO																										
UserId	2																										
Azimuth																											
Altitude																											
Elevation																											
Accuracy																											
URI	https://imagecloudstorage.scen-project.eu/kifisos/image/VmXCxZ88Sofox4AoUtl6.jpg																										
Status	Valid																										
Timestamp	20/06/2019 8:59:42 AM																										
Position	(37.91754,23.71735)																										
EventType	Blocked.River																										
CriticalityLevel	Low																										
FreeText																											

Table 20 Data Translator for Temperature feature store

<pre>{ "datasetId": "15cf22ff3eac536.72418950", "geoSensorCoord": { "accuracy": 7.504, "elevation": 20.19158935546875, "latitude": 45.23810613, "longitude": 29.13626318 }, "measurementList": [{ "takenAt": 1559375859000, "type": "temperature", "unit": "celcius", "value": 32.6 }, { "takenAt": 1559375859000, "type": "moisture", "unit": "percentage", "value": 19 }], "sensorId": "C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5", "trustLevel": 0, }</pre>	<table border="1"> <tr><td>TemperatureId</td><td>15cf22ff3eac536.72418950</td></tr> <tr><td>UserId</td><td>1427</td></tr> <tr><td>Azimuth</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Altitude</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Elevation</td><td>20.19158</td></tr> <tr><td>Accuracy</td><td>7.504</td></tr> <tr><td>Timestamp</td><td>1/06/2019 7:57:39 AM</td></tr> <tr><td>Position</td><td>(45.2381,29.13626)</td></tr> <tr><td>SensorId</td><td>C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5</td></tr> <tr><td>Value</td><td>32.6</td></tr> <tr><td>UnitOfMeasure</td><td>Celsius</td></tr> <tr><td>TrustLevel</td><td></td></tr> </table>	TemperatureId	15cf22ff3eac536.72418950	UserId	1427	Azimuth		Altitude		Elevation	20.19158	Accuracy	7.504	Timestamp	1/06/2019 7:57:39 AM	Position	(45.2381,29.13626)	SensorId	C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5	Value	32.6	UnitOfMeasure	Celsius	TrustLevel	
TemperatureId	15cf22ff3eac536.72418950																								
UserId	1427																								
Azimuth																									
Altitude																									
Elevation	20.19158																								
Accuracy	7.504																								
Timestamp	1/06/2019 7:57:39 AM																								
Position	(45.2381,29.13626)																								
SensorId	C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5																								
Value	32.6																								
UnitOfMeasure	Celsius																								
TrustLevel																									

<pre>{ "userId": "1427" }</pre>	
-----------------------------------	--

Table 21 Data Translator for Moisture feature store

<pre>{ "datasetId": "15cf22ff3eac536.72418950", "geoSensorCoord": { "accuracy": 7.504, "elevation": 20.19158935546875, "latitude": 45.23810613, "longitude": 29.13626318 }, "measurementList": [{ "takenAt": 1559375859000, "type": "temperature", "unit": "celcius", "value": 32.6 }, { "takenAt": 1559375859000, "type": "moisture", "unit": "percentage", "value": 19 }], "sensorId": "C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5", "trustLevel": 0, "userId": "1427" }</pre>	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td>MoistureId</td> <td>15cf22ff3eac536.72418950</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UserId</td> <td>1427</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Azimuth</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Altitude</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Elevation</td> <td>20.19158</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Accuracy</td> <td>7.504</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Timestamp</td> <td>1/06/2019 7:57:39 AM</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Position</td> <td>(45.2381,29.13626)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SensorId</td> <td>C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Value</td> <td>19</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UnitOfMeasure</td> <td>Percentage</td> </tr> <tr> <td>TrustLevel</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	MoistureId	15cf22ff3eac536.72418950	UserId	1427	Azimuth		Altitude		Elevation	20.19158	Accuracy	7.504	Timestamp	1/06/2019 7:57:39 AM	Position	(45.2381,29.13626)	SensorId	C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5	Value	19	UnitOfMeasure	Percentage	TrustLevel	
MoistureId	15cf22ff3eac536.72418950																								
UserId	1427																								
Azimuth																									
Altitude																									
Elevation	20.19158																								
Accuracy	7.504																								
Timestamp	1/06/2019 7:57:39 AM																								
Position	(45.2381,29.13626)																								
SensorId	C4:7C:8D:65:E6:F5																								
Value	19																								
UnitOfMeasure	Percentage																								
TrustLevel																									

For the SensorThings API the correlation between the received data and the data model is not so straightforward. For each data object received, one Observation entity and one FeatureOfInterest entity are created. In order for these entities to be valid, in the context of the standard, the Observation entity has to be associated with a Datastream. A Datastream is a unique combination of a Thing, Sensor and ObservedProperty entities.

The pre-defined the ObservedProperties based on the information collected in the project include:

- Water level
- Water velocity
- Air Temperature
- Soil moisture
- LC/LU

Each volunteer is modelled as a Thing entity, based on the unique user identifier that is available in the received metadata. Each portable sensor is modelled as a Sensor entity, based on the sensor unique identifier included in the metadata.

For the data that do not require a portable sensor, the mobile device of the volunteer, uniquely matched to the volunteer is used as a Sensor entity. An example of the data translation process of video metadata collected Kifisos river basin to SensorThings API compliant data model is presented in Figure 3.

In this case, the ObservedProperty entity is the water velocity, whilst the longitude and the latitude constitute the location of the observation which corresponds to the FeatureOfInterest entity and the Location entity of the Thing at that time. The Thing and the Sensor entities are identified by the user id.

```

{
  "videoid": 2670,
  "pilot": "kifisos",
  "geoCamCoor": {
    "longitude": 23.7248630523682,
    "latitude": 38.0239715576172
  },
  "crowdURI": "https://imagecloudstorage.scent-project.eu/kifisos/video/DUfYRDKBt5YclE1C2mx.mp4",
  "validation": {
    "conf": 0.11991010760107512,
    "isValid": "true"
  },
  "ObservedProperty": {
    "waterVelocity": 0.1413767151817979,
    "takenAt": 1561282680,
    "status": "Annotated",
    "fps": 29.384328358208954,
    "source": {
      "Id": 652,
      "type": "scentUser"
    }
  }
}

```

FeatureOfInterest/ Location

Observation

Thing/ Sensor

Figure 3 Data Translator video example

5.2.2 In-situ measurements

The majority of environmental data is traditionally collected through in-situ monitoring stations. In-situ sensing can be defined as a technology used to acquire information about an object when distance between the object and the sensor is comparable to or smaller than any linear dimension of the sensor. A short dictionary-based definition for in-situ sensing could be “sensing in place”.

In the context of SCENT, five in-situ monitoring stations have been installed on the Kifisos pilot area, measuring water level on the river in different times and under different weather conditions. In all locations, data loggers are connected to the in-situ sensors and offer the possibility to either download the data in-situ (using dedicated software), or remotely transfer the data through the use of the built in GSM/GPRS modem.

In the context of SCENT, as shown in Figure 4, the data loggers have been configured to send the measurement values in the form of csv-like files onto an SFTP server. The lack of interoperability in the aforementioned files dictated the need to deploy into the SFTP server an executable JAR (Java ARchive) file that is in charge of transforming the csv-like files into JSON and pass the measurements in the Harmonisation Platform Back-End endpoint. The end result is to have all in-situ measurements stored in the Harmonisation Platform Back-End in SensorThings API compatible format.

However, it should be noted that before the storage of the in-situ measurements in the back-end, the measurements go through the Data Quality Module in order to apply an effective quality control of the values and their dates (i.e. observe possible delays, fault data, etc.). The functionalities and responsibilities of the Data Quality Control Module (e.g. alerts, automatic filtering, etc.) for the in-situ sensors are analysed in chapter 6.2.

Figure 4 Data flow for in-situ measurements

Table 22 provides a shorten example of in-situ measurements collected from Kokkinos Mylos in-situ station in the form of csv-like format and the SensorThings API compatible translation.

Table 22 Data translator for in-situ measurements

<p>__Q_10 S20 049H0545 KOK_MYL NAMES mAmperes</p> <p>Index DateTime Ch2/A/C/av 719#126 07-07-19,12:15:00 0.0840 3.4630 719#141 07-07-19,12:30:00 0.1124 3.4630 719#156 07-07-19,12:45:00 0.1078 3.4630 719#171 07-07-19,13:00:00 0.1005 3.4630</p>	<pre>[{ "Datastream": { "@iot.id": 4 }, "dataArray": [["2019-07-07T12:15:00+02:00", "2019-07-07T12:15:00+02:00", "0.0840", 4], ["2019-07-07T12:30:00+02:00", "2019-07-07T12:30:00+02:00", "0.1124", 4], ["2019-07-07T12:45:00+02:00", "2019-07-07T12:45:00+02:00", "0.1078", 4], ["2019-07-07T12:45:00+02:00", "2019-07-07T12:45:00+02:00", "0.1078", 4], ["2019-07-07T12:45:00+02:00", "2019-07-07T12:45:00+02:00", "0.1078", 4]] }]</pre>
--	---

	<pre> ["2019-07- 07T13:00:00+02:00", "2019-07- 07T13:00:00+02:00", "0.1005", 4]], "components": ["phenomenonTime", "resultTime", "result", "FeatureOfInterest/id"], "dataArray@iot.count": 4 }] </pre>
--	---

5.2.3 Raster Data

The main goal for the raster data is to ensure the uniformity of the spatial information. To this end all data received in raster form are transformed to the EPSG:4326, also known as WGS84, global reference system.

WGS 84 is an Earth-centered, Earth-fixed terrestrial reference system and geodetic datum. It is based on a consistent set of constants and model parameters that describe the Earth's size, shape, and gravity and geomagnetic fields, and is the reference system for the Global Positioning System (GPS).

Given that our main source of spatial information is crowd-sourced data collected by volunteers using mobile devices, which provide their position using the WGS reference system it is essential to ensure that this is followed also by the spatially continuous information.

6 Data Quality

6.1 Crowd sourced measurements

6.1.1 Methodology

During the crowd-sourced campaigns, the measurements collected by the volunteers with the use of portable sensors could contain fault data, such as wrong location provided from the smartphone of each user or wrong measurements from the sensors (soil moisture, air temperature). This section describes the methods that were followed in order to locate these measurements that will be considered as invalid. As result, each user is associated with a score.

In order to locate the fault measurements, firstly the collected data are presented in plots describing their numerical and spatial distributions. Afterwards, methods of statistics and clustering analysis were used. The two pilot areas (Kifisos river basin and Danube Delta) are analysed separately in the following sections. For each area the temperature and moisture collected data are also separately analysed.

The analysed data, consist of: i) 248 and 510 measurements collected during the 2nd (November 2018) and 4th (April 2019) & 5th (June 2019) field campaigns in Kifisos river basin respectively, and ii)

1313 and 1027 measurements collected during the 4th (May 2019) and 5th (June 2019) field campaigns in Danube Delta respectively. Those data contain:

- Location of each measurement
- GPS accuracy (collected from the GPS sensor of the smartphones)
- Elevation from sea surface. Data with elevation equal to zero are considered as fault data and have been excluded from the databases.
- Air Temperature measurements
- Soil Moisture measurements.

Before processing the data, measurements collected at wrong time periods or wrong spatial distribution were excluded (i.e. data collected from the participant during the training/preparatory activities before the execution of the field visits).

For the Kifisos river basin, the spatial distribution consisted of 4 different areas, data were clustered into groups. In order to make this separation into groups, the k-means clustering algorithm (Appendix A1 and (S. Lloyd,1982)) was applied to the coordinates of the collected data. The k-means clustering algorithm splits multidimensional data into a total of k groups, called clusters. The resulting clusters must include data with 'similar' values. By comparing the data inside each cluster separately dissimilarities can be easily discovered, and thus fault data can be revealed (range test). The k-means algorithm used, was programmed using the MATLAB software and is described in Appendix A1.

In addition, in the context of the citizen science campaigns of the project, a score is associated with each of the activities conducted by the user. For each collected measurement by the user, a positive point (+1) is assigned as a score. In case the measurement is considered in a later stage as fault or partially fault, then penalties are provided to users that provided the measurements. In particular, the penalties associate negative score points to the users whose measurements included wrong elevation and/or location and/or temperature values. Thus, the user's total score is being formulate by the sum of positive and negative score points. The following table presents the method that the penalties are calculated for the air temperature data. In addition, it should be noted that the score is stored only internally and is not presented to the users.

Table 23 Matrix for the calculation of air temperature penalties

Temperature Measuring Penalties		
Responsible	Issue	Penalty
Sensor	Temperature constantly out of average / expected values, while a specific sensor is used by different users	-1
Sensor	Temperature constantly out of "logical" values (e.g. -15 ° C in December at the city of Athens)	-1
User	Temperature constantly out of average/ expected values, while using different sensors	-1
User	A few measurements that were contributed initially are outliers (inexperience)	-0.3
Sensor	Temperature measurements not having similar values with nearby measurements	-1

The soil moisture data collected by the portable sensors constitute integer values representing the percentage of the soil moisture into the soil.

While searching the soil moisture database for erroneous measurements, data with elevation or soil moisture values equal to zero were discovered. The zero elevation is considered as fault data. The challenging part is to discover if values of soil moisture equal to zero have occurred by measuring while the sensor isn't inserted inside the soil or if they occurred by measuring dry soil. As we have checked in laboratory tests, the moisture sensor can result a 0% moisture level when measuring dry soil without any roots of alive plants inside, which is reasonable since the soil in such cases behaves as an infinite resistance (zero conductivity). In order to validate the zero moisture levels as fault data or not, the following test was applied: if a user provided a 0% moisture level and within the next 15 seconds (the sensors give new measurements every 15 seconds) he provided a measurement greater than 0%, then his first measurement is considered as fault; this test will be called as the 15"-test into this section. This test is also known as 'sigma test' or 'delta test' in bibliography (Taylor, J. R., & Loescher, H. L. (2013))

The method used here to associate negative scores to fault moisture measuring is presented in Table 24. Moreover, the general penalties applied are also presented below (Table 25).

Table 24 Matrix for the calculation of air temperature penalties

Moisture Penalties		
Responsible	Issue	Penalty
Sensor	Moisture constantly out of average/expected, while used by different users	-1
User	Moisture constantly out of average/expected, while using different sensors	-1
User	Wrong moisture level (15" check) (inexperience)	- 0.3

Table 25 Matrix for the calculation of general penalties.

General/Common Penalties			
Responsible	Issue	Penalty	Way to identify this case
User/Device	Elevation=0, faulty device or compatibility error	-0.2	GPS elevation = 0
User/Device	GPS location not in the ROI (Region of Interest) as expected, device used at a non-pilot area	-0.4	GPS coordinates not in the experiment's area
User	Temperature correct but moisture 0%, sensor not inserted in the soil	-0.5	
User	Temperature incorrect, moisture correct. Not expected to be encountered, used harmful intent	-1	

6.1.2 Analysis of data collected from citizen-science campaigns in Kifisos river basin

6.1.2.1 Air temperature

The analysis presented below refers to the data collected during the 2nd field campaign in Kifisos. While searching the database for fault measurements, the elevation and air temperature values appeared to have reasonable measurements (Figure 5). Further to this, the data were separated into $k = 4$ different clusters according to their spatial distribution (Figure 6).

Figure 5 Histograms showing the elevation and the temperature measurements in the collected database.

Figure 6 The Temperature data separated into 4 different clusters, according to the location of each measurement

In the context of the campaigns, small groups of people (3-6) were collecting data in each area (cluster) and each of them was measuring the air temperature at a nearby place with the others. So, in each of the 4 clusters, similar measurements at similar timestamps should be expected. Figure 7 shows the histograms of these values in order to locate more fault data.

Figure 7 Histograms of descriptive statistics (time of measurement, temperature and elevation) for each cluster

Based on this analysis, the temperature data of Clusters #1 and #2 seem to be uniformly distributed around the minimum and maximum values, but in Clusters #3 and #4 this doesn't seem to happen. For instance, after exploring the data, in Cluster #3 one user (the one with ID 955) was discovered to record small temperature values only at the beginning of his measurements (probably the sensor was initially placed in a colder place); yet his subsequent measurements were considered to be acceptable. Also, in Cluster #4 one user (the one with ID 963) was sending higher temperature measurements than the other users (Figure 8).

Figure 8 A Box-Plot presenting the temperature values that flagged users in Cluster #4 provided

In order to prove the difference of the measurements of this user, the One-Way ANOVA statistical test (Welch,1952) was applied to these data (Table 26). The test resulted that the differences between the data of different users of Cluster #4 are significant ($p = 6.47 \cdot 10^{-34} < 0.01$), so it can be assumed that the user #963 provided fault measurements.

Table 26 The One-way ANOVA table that compares the differences of mean values of the temperature data collected by different users in the Cluster #4.

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob>F
Groups	499.2218	3	166.4073	251.2404	6.47E-34
Error	39.74056	60	0.662343		
Total	538.9623	63			

The temperature's fault data discovered in the collected database are:

- The users with IDs 951, 961, and 3 times the 963 have provided temperature data with location outside our region of interest (ROI), so each of these measurements is associated with -0.4 points.
- The users with IDs 955, 955, 958, 955, 963, 955, 955, 955, 955, 963, 951, 955, 955, 955, 955, 952 (duplicates exist) have provided data with zero elevation.
- Also the user 963 has provided temperature data outside the range of the other users while being on the area called Cluster #4. When the same user was located at the area of Cluster #2, he provided reasonable temperature measurements, so he is not using a malfunctioning sensor, but something was wrong with his measuring process. Those penalties are presented in Table 27.

Table 27 Total penalties for the users that provided air temperature data (2nd field campaign in Kifisos river basin)

		UserID:	951	952	955	958	961	963
Reason of fault data	Elevation = 0	Frequency	1	1	11	1		2
	GPS location not in the ROI		1				1	3
	Temperature measurements not having similar values with nearby measurements							1
		Total Score Points	-0.6	-0.2	-2.2	-0.2	-0.4	-2.6

6.1.2.2 Soil moisture

The distribution of the collected moisture data for the Kifisos area is presented in Figure 9. The collected data were again clustered into the previous 4 clusters, whose distribution is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 9 A Histogram representing the measurements of the moisture in the database

Figure 10. Histograms of descriptive statistics (time of measurement, soil moisture and elevation)

The 15"-test resulted negative points for providing wrong measurements to the users with the IDs: 0 (2 times), 931 (2 times), 955 (4 times), 962 (2 times) and 963(3 times). Furthermore, users providing zero elevation were excluded from the database (951, 952, 955 (10 times), 958, 963 (2 times)). These results are presented in Table 28.

Table 28 Fault score points for the Moisture database.

UserID:		0	931	951	952	955	958	962	963
15"-test	Frequency	2	2			4		2	3
Elevation = 0				1	1	10	1		2
Total Fault Points		-0.6	-0.6	-0.2	-0.2	-3.2	-0.2	-0.6	-1.3

The total of the fault scores assigned to the users from the air temperature and soil moisture measuring activities during the 2nd field campaign in the Kifisos river basin is presented in the following table (Table 29).

Table 29 Total fault scores from Temperature and Moisture databases (2nd field campaign in Kifisos river basin).

	UserID	0	931	951	952	955	958	961	962	963
Fault points from measuring of	Temperature			-0.6	-0.2	-2.2	-0.2	-0.4		-2.6
	Moisture	-0.6	-0.6	-0.2	-0.2	-3.2	-0.2		-0.6	-1.3
	TOTAL	-0.6	-0.6	-0.8	-0.4	-5.4	-0.4	-0.4	-0.6	-3.9

The same analysis was applied for the data collected (N = 510) in the 4th and 5th field campaigns in Kifisos river basin. The outputs of the analysis and the fault scores assigned are presented in the following table.

Table 30 Total Fault scores for the data collected during the 4th and 5th field campaigns in Kifisos

	Temperature measuring				Soil Moisture measuring			TOTAL
User ID	Elevation = 0	GPS location not in the ROI	Temperature measurements not having similar values with nearby measurements	Negative Points from temperature measuring	15'' -- test	Elevation = 0	Negative Points from moisture measuring	
4	2	1		-0.8	4	2	-1.6	-2.4
12		3		-1.2	3		-0.9	-2.1
16	32			-6.4	1	31	-6.5	-12.9
17					1		-0.3	-0.3
19	2	1		-0.8		2	-0.4	-1.2
604	2	2		-1.2	1	2	-0.7	-1.9
1300	16	18		-10.4	12	16	-6.8	-17.2
1445	5	1		-1.4	5	5	-2.5	-3.9
1452	56			-11.2		56	-11.2	-22.4

6.1.3 Analysis of data collected from citizen-science campaigns in Danube Delta

As mentioned in the previous sections, the collected measurements in Danube Delta area can also contain data that don't correspond to campaigns or to specific points of interest (i.e. collected during training activities). Such data are being discarded and are not passed through the data quality control system.

6.1.3.1 Air temperature

The analysis presented below refers to the data collected during the 4th field campaign in Danube Delta. The air temperature measurements collected, consist of reasonable values, ranging between 18.8-32.9 °C (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Histogram of the elevation and temperature values of the measurements

Measurements with erroneous elevation values were discovered in the database. In particular, elevation values lower than 12 meters are considered as fault measurement for the Danube Delta area. A total of 156 measurements located far away from the area/points of interest were considered as fault measurements too.

Those fault measurements in the database are:

- The users with IDs : 19 (22 times), 72 (70 times), 73 (2 times), 1322 (5 times), 1393 (23 times), 1397 (8 times), 1400 (12 times), 1401 (140 times), 1404 (5 times) provided data with elevation $\leq 12m$, so each of these measurements is associated with -0.2 points.
- The users with IDs : 19 (3), 72 (3), 73 (2), 1322 (5), 1393 (124), 1397 (7), 1400 (5), 1401 (5), 1404 (2) provided temperature data with coordinates outside the experiment’s area, so each of these measurements is associated with -0.4 points. Inside parenthesis, the frequency of the wrong measurements is provided.

Figure 12. Overview of the measurements with non-fault location values

Following the penalties methods that described earlier, Table 31 summarizes the fault points resulted from the air temperature measuring activities.

Table 31. Total penalties for the users that provided the temperature data.

UserID		19	72	73	1322	1393	1397	1400	1401	1404
Wrong Elevation	Frequency	22	70	2	5	23	8	12	140	5
Wrong GPS location provided		3	3	2	5	124	7	5	5	2
Negative Score		-5.6	-15.2	-1.2	-3	-54.2	-4.4	-4.4	-30	-1.8

6.1.3.2 Soil moisture

The distribution of the soil moisture level is presented on Figure 13.

Figure 13. The moisture values in the database

The 15th-test was used to reveal the fault zero moisture measurements. These discovered fault data are presented on Table 32.

Table 32 The users who provided data with fault moisture measuring

UserID	19	1304	1393	1397	1400	1404
frequency	3	1	9	4	7	3
Negative Score	-0.9	-0.3	-2.7	-1.2	-2.1	-0.9

Table 33 summarizes the faults points each user gained from Table 31 and Table 32 during the 4th field campaign in Danube Delta.

Table 33. Total fault scores from Temperature and Moisture databases (4th field campaign in Danube Delta)

USER ID	19	72	73	1304	1322	1393	1397	1400	1401	1404
Temperature	-5.6	-15.2	-1.2		-3	-54.2	-4.4	-4.4	-30	-1.8
Moisture	-0.9			-0.3		-2.7	-1.2	-2.1		-0.9
SUM	-6.5	-15.2	-1.2	-0.3	-3	-56.9	-5.6	-6.5	-30	-2.7

The same analysis was performed for the measurements collected during the 5th campaign in Danube Delta and the outputs of the analysis and the fault scores assigned are presented in the table below.

Table 34 Total fault scores for data collected during the 5th field campaign in Danube Delta

User ID	Air temperature measuring				Soil moisture measuring			TOTAL
	Elevation = 0	GPS location not in the ROI	Temperature measurements not having similar values with nearby measurements	Negative Points from air temperature measuring	15" -- test	Elevation = 0	Negative Points from soil moisture measuring	
19	1	79		-31.8	2	1	-0.8	-32.6
72	13	1		-3	2	5	-1.6	-4.6
73	2	2		-1.2		2	-0.4	-1.6
1322	2	3		-1.6	4	2	-1.6	-3.2
1391	42	7		-11.2		13	-2.6	-13.8
1392		8		-3.2			0	-3.2
1403	1	4		-1.8	2	1	-0.8	-2.6
1411	1	2		-1	2	1	-0.8	-1.8
1412	2	3		-1.6	2	2	-1	-2.6
1419		157		-62.8	1		-0.3	-63.1
1422	3	4		-2.2	2	3	-1.2	-3.4
1423	3	4		-2.2	4	3	-1.8	-4
1424	5	9		-4.6		5	-1	-5.6
1425	7	12		-6.2	4	6	-2.4	-8.6
1426	1	1		-0.6	1	1	-0.5	-1.1
1427	4	8		-4	2	4	-1.4	-5.4
1430	2	1		-0.8	3	1	-1.1	-1.9

6.2 In-situ measurements

As stated in Chapter 5 and depicted in Figure 4, the measurements from the in-situ sensors undergo both translation and data quality control, before their storage in the distributed database layer. Both the Translation and Quality Control services are being implemented by the JAR file that has been deployed in the SFTP Server. While the Data Translator converts the csv-like that has been received from the data logger into SensorThings API format, the Data Quality control acts as an alert mechanism and as an effective filter concerning the sensor measurements. Thereafter, the following functionalities are part of the Quality Control unit:

- Delay Alerts and Notifications:** The Data Quality Control unit checks for delays regarding the delivery of the in-situ sensor measurements which are supposed to arrive at the SFTP server once per day. In case of delays whatever the reason (sensor malfunction, data logger

communication barriers, etc.) alert emails are being sent. It has to be noted that the Data Quality Control checks for delays once per day and in case of detected problems, relevant info is included in the email body (stations responsible for the delay, the actual delay in measured in hours, etc.).

- **Low Battery Alerts:** As shown in Table 22, the battery value is included in the sensor measurements file received from the data logger. Thereafter, in case of low battery value (less than 3.3 Volts) an alert email is being sent in order to notify partners about the specific in-situ station that needs to be checked.
- **Alerts in case of deviation of the measured value from the accepted reference value:** In some cases, sensor measurement values may be wrong, do not make sense and do not represent the environmental conditions because of malfunctioning. In this case, when the water level values from the in-situ stations are not within the range of 0-1 meter, a relevant notification email is being sent to partners indicating the station and the relevant sensor measurements file that need to be checked. The upper threshold has been assigned considering historical information about the water level in the areas where the in-situ sensors are located. In this use case, even if the measurement values need to be checked, (thanks to the notification email), these are stored in the Harmonisation Platform.
- **Automatic Filtering of In-Situ measurements:** The Data Quality Control unit automatically filters the water level measurements in a way that negative values and/or values that exceed the maximum depth of the river cross section are not being stored in the Harmonisation Platform.

7 Data Provision

7.1 SensorThings API

We have implemented the API for the SensorThings API standard as a standalone Tomcat application using the Jersey RESTful Web Services framework. The implementation supports all the requests described in the standard as well as all the filtering capabilities. The implementation has successfully passed all 22 tests, for conformance levels 1-2-3 which are available in the online test suit¹³ and has received the certifications as an OGC compliant implementation. The Web Application Description Language (WADL) of the service presenting all the provided endpoints is included in Appendix A2. We present here an overview of the endpoints provided.

The OGC SensorThings API service groups the same types of entities into entity sets. Each entity has a unique identifier and one-to-many properties. Also, in the case of an entity holding a relationship with entities in other entity sets, this type of relationship is expressed with navigation properties.

Therefore, in order to perform CRUD actions on the resources, the first step is to address to the target resources through URI. There are three major URI components used here, namely (1) the service root URI, (2) the resource path, and (3) the query options.

Service Root URI

The root URI of the service is <http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/>. It provides as a response a JSON object with a property named value. The value of this property is a JSON Array containing one element for each entity set of the SensorThings Service.

Each element is a JSON object with at least two name/value pairs, one with name containing the name of the entity set (e.g., Things, Locations, Datastreams, Observations, ObservedProperties and Sensors) and one with name url containing the URL of the entity set. The returned JSON object is:

```
{
  "value": [{
    "name": "Things",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Things"
  }, {
    "name": "Locations",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Locations"
  }, {
    "name": "HistoricalLocations",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/HistoricalLocations"
  }, {
    "name": "Datastreams",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Datastreams"
  }, {
    "name": "Sensors",
```

¹³ <http://cite.opengeospatial.org/te2/>


```

    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Sensors"
  }, {
    "name": "Observations",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Observations"
  }, {
    "name": "ObservedProperties",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/ObservedProperties"
  }, {
    "name": "FeaturesOfInterest",
    "url": "http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/FeaturesOfInterest"
  }
}

```

GET Requests

The data are available in many ways that can be categorized as follows:

Table 35 GET Requests available

Category	URI pattern	Result
Collection of entities	SERVICE_ROOT_URI/ ENTITY_SET_NAME	A list of all entities in the specified entity set when there is no service-driven pagination imposed. The response is represented as a JSON object containing a name/value pair named value, a JSON array where each element is representation of an entity or of an entity reference.
Entity in a collection	SERVICE_ROOT_URI/ ENTITY_SET_NAME (ID_OF_THE_ENTITY)	A JSON object of the entity that holds the specified id in the entity set.
Property of an entity	SERVICE_ROOT_URI/ RESOURCE_PATH_TO_AN_ENTITY/ PROPERTY_NAME	The specified property of an entity that holds the id in the entity set.
Value of an entity's property	SERVICE_ROOT_URI/ ENTITY_SET_NAME (ID_OF_THE_ENTITY)/ PROPERTY_NAME/\$value	The raw value of the specified property of an entity that holds the id in the entity set.
A navigation property	SERVICE_ROOT_URI/ ENTITY_SET_NAME (ID_OF_THE_ENTITY)/LINK_NAME	A JSON object of one entity or a JSON array of many entities that holds a certain relationship with the specified entity.
An association link	SERVICE_ROOT_URI/	A JSON object with a value

	ENTITY_SET_NAME (KEY_OF_THE_ENTITY)/ LINK_NAME/\$ref	property, a JSON array containing one element for each associationLink. Each element is a JSON object with a pair, with name url and the value of selfLinks of the related entities.
--	--	--

In addition to the URIs above, the API supports a range of query functionalities. These are:

- **\$filter:** allows clients to filter a collection of entities that are addressed by a request URL. The SensorThings API supports a set of functions that can be used in this query operation. We present in Appendix A3 the tables with all the filter operators and the functions required by the standard and supported by our implementation.
- **\$count:** specifies that the total count of items within a collection matching the request is returned along with the result. The default value is false.
- **\$orderby:** specifies the order in which items are returned from the service. The value of the \$orderby system query option may contain a comma-separated list of expressions whose primitive result values are used to sort the items.
- **\$skip:** specifies the number for the items of the queried collection that are excluded from the result. The value of \$skip system query option is a non-negative integer n.
- **\$top:** the limit on the number of items returned from a collection of entities. The value of the \$top system query option is a non-negative integer n.
- **\$expand:** indicates the related entities to be represented inline. The value of the \$expand query option is a comma separated list of navigation property names.
- **\$select:** the service returns only the properties explicitly requested by the client. The value of a \$select query option is a comma-separated list of selection clauses. Each selection clause SHALL be a property name or a navigation property.

POST requests

To create an entity in a collection, the client sends a HTTP POST request to that collection's URL. The POST body contains a single valid entity representation. If the target URL for the collection is a navigationLink, the new entity is automatically linked to the entity containing the navigationLink.

Newly created entities may be linked to existing entities, by using the entity id, or contain the information needed to create the related entities. A request to create an entity that includes related entities, represented using the appropriate inline representation, is referred to as a "deep insert".

PATCH requests

HTTP PATCH requests are responsible to merge the content in the request payload with the entity's current state, applying the update only to those components specified in the request body. The properties provided in the payload corresponding to updatable properties replace the value of the corresponding property in the entity. Missing properties of the containing entity or complex properties are not directly altered.

These requests may contain binding information for navigation properties. For single-valued navigation properties this replaces the relationship. For collection-valued navigation properties this adds to the relationship.

DELETE requests

A successful DELETE request to an entity's edit URL deletes the entity. The request body must be empty. The implementation implicitly removes relations to and from an entity when deleting it; clients need not delete the relations explicitly. Related entities may be deleted or modified if required by integrity constraints.

7.2 WFS/ WMS

The WFS/WMS standard defines the framework for providing access to, and supporting transactions on, discrete geographic features in a manner that is independent of the underlying data source. Through complex query operations, users have access to the source spatial and attribute data in a manner that allows them to download individual features.

The query operations over the WFS/WMS services, filter functions, are provided by the GeoServer¹⁴ and are compliant with the OGC Filter Encoding¹⁵ specification. A filter function is a named function with any number of arguments, which can be used in a filter expression to perform specific calculations. This provides much richer expressiveness for defining filters. Filter functions can be used in both the XML Filter Encoding language and the textual ECQL language, using the syntax appropriate to the language.

7.3 Custom API

In order to facilitate the access to the information by the Campaign Manager and the Explore App, we have created a custom API that provides the information in a uniform way. This API is created as a standalone Tomcat application using the Jersey RESTful Web Services framework.

To begin with there is a specific URI format that can be utilized to get the needed information. The format is:

<base_uri>/<resource_requested>?<pilot>&<bb>&<time_range>&<id>&<property_name>&<tag>&<format>

The <base_uri> refers to the server where the information is stored.

The <resource_requested> may be image, video, event report, sensor metadata, air temperature or soil moisture.

The filter parameters are optional, can be used simultaneously or independently and are:

- <pilot>: can be either kifisos or danube
- <bb>: should include the four corners of a rectangle
- <time_range>: one or two timestamps indicating the time span for the resources

¹⁴ https://docs.geoserver.org/latest/en/user/filter/function_reference.html#filter-function-reference

¹⁵ <https://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/filter>

- <id>: the feature id, in case all the information for only one id is needed
- <property_name>: returns only the specified properties for the features included in the result
- <tag>: this additional filter is available only for the images, and performs a keyword search in list containing all the validated tags referring to this image
- <format>: this filter indicates if the result should be a GeoJSON or a GML file.

8 Visualisation Site

8.1 SensorThings API Frond-End

The SCENT visualisation site is a client application (<http://scent-harm.iccs.gr/>) tailored for the purposes of inspecting and visualizing traditional in-situ and citizen-generated observations. All SCENT resources (measurements derived from in-situ or volunteers' portable sensors) that have been stored in the Harmonisation Platform back-end can be displayed to the users through the use of pertinent maps, graphs, tables or files. The visualisation site constitutes an innovative front-end single-page application that is conformant with OGC SensorThings API standard, and thereafter, it is generic enough to be integrated with any back-end that exposes resources compliant to the aforementioned protocol.

Its user-friendly interfaces enable both time-series analysis and spatial representation of SensorThings API resources as follows (more details regarding the Visualisation Site functionalities along with the screenshots are provided in next chapter):

- Time-series analysis of the observations filtered by the observed phenomenon and the sensor.
- Presentation on the map of the latest known locations of all the Data Providers (campaign volunteers in the case of SCENT)
- Visualisation of the Data Providers location path.
- Simultaneous visualisation of the observations in relation to time and space for a given Observed Phenomenon and a given Data Provider
- Presentation of all measurements metadata on the map, filtered by the available Observed Phenomena

8.2.1 Implementation details

The Harmonisation Front End platform is a single-page application, developed with modern frameworks which features an adoptable architecture. The integration of the visualisation site with the back-end and the Identity and Access management Server is depicted in the following figure.

Figure 14 Integration of the Harmonisation Platform front-end with the back-end and the Identity Management Server

As shown in Figure 14, the following entities interact with the front-end:

- **NginX¹⁶**: It routes incoming traffic to either Node.js or Identity Manager. To this end, NginX has been configured as a reverse proxy and distributes the load among Node.js¹⁷ Server and Identity Manager Server. Proxying is being conducted seamlessly for the end-user across HTTP, depending on the case (e.g. NginX passes the HTTP request to the Identity Manager in case of Authorisation or to Node.js in case of serving static content (html, css, javascript, etc..).)
- **Node.js**: It serves pages on incoming requests. The Node.js Server provides the user with the front-end app content (html, css, javascript, navigation).
- **Back-end**: It provides endpoints compliant to OGC SensorThings API definitions in order for the front-end to be able to fetch the relevant resources according to user requests. The data services are always provided in the form of JSON.
- **Identity Manager**: It provides authorisation services and it has been implemented with Keycloak¹⁸.

Regarding the security, as shown in Figure 14, the visualisation site has been integrated with an Identity and Access Manager. The Identity Manager runs as a separate server and it adds authentication to both the front-end and back-end parts of the Harmonisation Platform. It has been incorporated so as to secure the SCENT Harmonisation Platform resources from unauthorized access. Thereafter, the security mechanism has been implemented with a Keycloak instance which

¹⁶ <https://www.nginx.com/resources/wiki/>

¹⁷ <https://nodejs.dev/>

¹⁸ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

holds the database of the Harmonisation Platform users and groups. Figure 15 presents the authentication workflow that needs to be followed in order for the client (user) to access a protected resource.

Figure 15 The Workflow that has to be followed in order for a user to authenticate and access a protected SCENT resource

According to Figure 15, the following steps need to be taken:

1. The user is willing through the browser to access a protected Harmonisation Platform resource. Therefore, the Harmonisation Platform Front-End part (Vue.js app) redirects the user to the Identity Manager in order to authenticate.
2. After successful authentication, the Identity Manager redirects the user back to the Front-End component. The Front-End component now also holds the corresponding JSON web token (JWT).
3. The Front-End component contacts the Back-End through the relevant web service. In order for the endpoint to be accessed, the Front-End passes through the HTTP Authorisation Request Header the token retrieved in the previous step.
4. The Harmonisation Platform Back-end verifies the token:
 - a. It checks that JWT is well formed.
 - b. It checks the signature
 - c. It validates the standard claims
 - d. It checks the application permissions (scopes)

5. In case of successful verification, the back-end offers the protected resource to the front-end.

The identity Manager offers user interfaces for changing its configuration, for creating new users, for creating new roles and for login/logout purposes. Also, relevant interfaces exist for defining certain user management policies and role-mappings. It also has to be noted that for the Harmonisation Platform a certain role has been created (entitled “scent-admin”) for restricting administrative privileges to few users (i.e. the Administrators). Figure 16 presents the screenshot for authenticating the user (login), Figure 17 presents the user registration interface and Figure 18 depicts information related to ‘scent-admin’.

Figure 16 The user authenticates to the Harmonisation Platform

Figure 17 A new user signs up for the Harmonisation Platform and thereafter creates a new account

Figure 18 The scent-admin role has been created in order to restrict advanced privileges to Administrators only

8.2.2 Functionalities

The aim of the Harmonisation Platform Front-End is to provide to the user a comprehensive overview of a variety of citizen-generated data as well as environmental data that have been collected through in-situ monitoring stations in Kifisos river basin, Attica, Greece. Maps and charts have been utilized so as for the user to be able to inspect in a user-friendly way the environmental conditions in certain periods.

It has to be noted that the visualisation site provides detailed explanation of its functionalities. Moreover, in addition to the visualisation facilities which are based on all resources compliant to SensorThings API, the visualisation site also includes a catalogue with links to GEOSS (Global Earth Observation System of Systems) portal for all metadata (of images, sensor measurements and event reports) exposed through WFS and WMS services. Figure 19 presents the Home page of the Harmonisation Platform.

Figure 19 Harmonisation Platform Home page

The user is being informed in the Home page about the available functionalities of the platform and the available catalogue of the data stored in the back-end. The links for accessing the platform functionalities exist on the top of the page, the link for authorizing the user is available on the top-right corner and the low-level info related to SensorThings entities is available on the left menu (“Sensors Dashboard”). The main functionalities of the Harmonisation Platform are the following:

Time Series analysis of the observations

This use case is for visualizing the sensor measurement values in relation to time. The user has to take the following steps:

1. Selection of the desired Observed Phenomenon (Air Temperature, Soil Moisture, Water Level, Water Velocity, etc.)

2. Selection of a Dataset. (It has to be noted that observation measurements are grouped to Datasets, according to the distinct relevant triple: Sensor - Data Provider – Observed Phenomenon)
3. Selection of a date range. The user selects through a calendar a date range for time-filtering of the observations
4. The user either selects “Load Observations” (for getting the chart) or “Download csv” (for downloading the csv file) buttons.

After the selection of the input parameters, as shown in Figure 20, the relevant chart is presented to the user:

Figure 20 Observations Chart in relation to time. The chart depicts the water level time-series for the in-situ sensor deployed in Monastiri. The sensor measurement values have been filtered from 1/6/2019 to 19/6/2019

It is worth mentioning that SCENT campaigns have been highlighted in the calendar and annotated with relevant description as shown in Figure 21 (e.g. days from 11/4/2019 to 14/4/2019 have been highlighted with info related to fourth campaign). Moreover, Figure 22 presents the screenshot for downloading the observations along with their metadata, instead of getting the chart.

Figure 21 Annotation of the calendar with information related to SCENT campaigns

Figure 22 The user downloads observation measurements in the form of csv file for the in-situ sensor deployed in Kokkinos Mylos

Data Providers Latest Locations

A Data Provider may be a human (e.g. a Campaign Volunteer in the case of portable sensors) or an IoT device, like a data logger in the case of in-situ sensors. As shown in Figure 23, the SCENT

Harmonisation Platform Front-End offers to the user the possibility to view on the map the latest known locations of all the Data Providers registered in the Back-End along with their pseudonym.

Figure 23 The latest known locations of the registered Data Providers is shown on the map along with their pseudonym

Data Providers Location Path

For the case of portable sensors, the location of the Data providers changes during the measurements. The SCENT Harmonisation Platform Back-End stores in the database the coordinates of all relevant locations of the Data Providers (Campaign Volunteers). Thereafter, as shown in Figure 24, the visualisation site is able to draw the historical location path of the chosen volunteer.

Figure 24 The historical location path of the chosen Data Provider (campaign volunteer in the case of SCENT) is shown in the map

Simultaneous presentations of measurements’ locations and values

Since both the measurement values and the locations of the observations are of equal importance with respect to environmental monitoring and improved mapping of the environment, a significant functionality of the visualisation site is the simultaneous presentation of a graph and a map which are being filled in real-time as time goes by. The steps are the following:

1. The user selects a Data Provider in order to inspect their measurement data.
2. Given the previous step, the user now selects the Observed Phenomenon and the Sensor that have been used for the aforementioned Campaign Volunteer.
3. The user presses the “Show” button.
4. A graph and a map are simultaneously populated with the measurement values and locations of the chosen triple Volunteer – Sensor – Observed Phenomenon.

This use case plays a major role for the user in the understanding of the variance of measurement values for a given Observed Phenomenon in relation to space. The screenshot concerning the simultaneous presentation of measurement values and location points through a chart and a map is included in Figure 25.

Figure 25 Both the measurement values (associated with water velocity) and the Volunteer’s (ID=1338) location path during the campaign are simultaneously displayed.

Observations filtered by given Observed Phenomena

In this use case, the user is able to view all the observations on the map, based on a selected Observed Phenomenon (e.g. Air Temperature, LC/LU, Soil Moisture, Water Level, Water Velocity). Based on the SensorThings API protocol that has been incorporated in the Back-End, all measurement observations are grouped in Observed Phenomenon categories. Thereafter, by choosing the desired Observed Phenomena in the checkboxes, the relevant observations can be displayed to the user through a map. As shown in Figure 26, the user is also able to click on a pin and

view the relevant observation metadata (dataset ID, observation result, measurement unit, observation phenomenon time).

Figure 26 The user is able to view on the map observation metadata given a chosen Observed Phenomenon. (here the temperature is being inspected in a given point on the map)

Low level Presentation of Harmonisation Platform database in the form of tables.

In addition to the high-level presentation of the sensor measurement values through the incorporation of charts and maps, the visualisation site also provides a low-level interaction with the Harmonisation Platform SensorThings API driven schema. To this end, pertinent tables are being used in order to present all the information of the SensorThings API database. There is one to one correlation between the Graphical User Interface (GUI) tables and the SensorThings API entities according to which the Harmonisation Platform database has been formed. Figure 27 presents the screenshot for rendering the Datastreams table (In SensorThings API, a Datastream is being used for grouping a collection of observations that measure the same Observed Property and produced by the same sensor).

IoT ID	Datastream Name	Datastream Description	Unit symbol	Unit Name	Unit Definition	Observation Type
96	This is a datastream with id 96	This is a datastream for user with id 94 while using sensor with id 91		LC/LU		OM_Measurement
97	This is a datastream with id 97	This is a datastream for user with id 95 while using sensor with id 92		LC/LU		OM_Measurement
98	This is a datastream with id 98	This is a datastream for user with id 96 while using sensor with id 93		LC/LU		OM_Measurement
99	This is a datastream with id 99	This is a datastream for user with id 97 while using sensor with id 94		LC/LU		OM_Measurement
1	Varympompi	This is a datastream for the water level sensor for Varympompi	m	WaterLevel	http://www.qudt.org/qudt/owl/1.0.0/unit/Instances.html#Meter	OM_Measurement

Figure 27 Datastreams Table.

As shown in Figure 27, the user is able to view all Datastreams stored in the Harmonisation Platform. The following functionalities are being offered through the user interface for all the tables (i.e. all SensorThings API entities):

- Pagination is being used for displaying a limited number of results each time.
- The user is able to order the records of the table based on a specific column
- The user is able to filter the table records according to the inserted text in one or more columns
- The user is able to add or delete records, as long as he has been authorized (i.e. the user has been assigned administrative privileges and therefore has been given “scent-admin” role permissions)

The Harmonisation Platform Front-End is an SPA (single-page application) and has been built with a client-side JavaScript framework (Vue.js). Thereafter, the visualisation site only holds static content (JavaScript logic and navigation rules, css, html, images, etc.). In order to visualize the resources (measurement values, sensor metadata, etc.) the visualisation site needs to call the APIs of the back-end. These APIs comply to the OGC SensorThings API standard and more specifically to the Part 1 of it, entitled “Sensing”. In the context of SCENT, the need to create web-based platforms that manage, store, share and analyse IoT-based sensor observation data, dictated the need for adopting such a protocol. Moreover, in addition to the simplification and the acceleration with respect to the development of IoT applications that this framework administers, the adoption of SensorThings API also provides enough flexibility in terms of interfaces homogeneity, effortless connection with other OGC standard-compliant servers and synchronisation. The following table outlines all the APIs definitions for all the functionalities that have been described before. Thereafter, each row of the

table corresponds to a specific API call that needs to be made in order for the Front-End to fetch the relevant resources and populate the graphs and maps.

Table 36 Services Consumption by the Harmonisation Platform Front-End

Gui Functionality	API call (examples)	Description
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time-series analysis of the observations filtered by the Observed Phenomenon and the Sensor 	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/ObservedProperties	This API is used for retrieving all the Observed Phenomena in order to populate the first dropdown list
	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/ObservedProperties(1)/Datastreams	This API is used for getting all the Datastreams given the previous selected Observed Phenomenon
	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Datastreams(5)/Observations?\$filter=phenomenonTime ge 2019-06-01T00:00:00.000Z and phenomenonTime le 2019-06-13T00:00:00.000Z&\$count=true	This API is used for getting all the observations that relate to the previous selected Datastream. In this example the observations are time filtered from 1/6/2019 to 13/6/2019.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Providers latest known location 	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Things?\$expand=HistoricalLocations(\$expand=Locations;\$stop=1;\$orderby=time desc)&\$stop=10&\$skip=0&\$count=true	This API is used for getting the latest known historical location for all Things (The Thing entity is considered to be a Campaign Volunteer in the case of SCENT). Pagination is being used through this API call for performance issues (e.g. in this example the latest locations of the first Data Provider is going to be fetched)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Providers Location path 	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Things	This API is used for getting all available Things (or else Data Providers)
	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Things(200)/HistoricalLocations?\$expand	This API is used for getting all historical locations (both time and coordinates) for the Thing (Data Provider in the case of

	=Locations	SCENT) that has been chosen in the previous step
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Simultaneous presentation of measurements' locations and values 	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Things	This API is used for getting all available things (or else Data Providers)
	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Things(181)/Datastreams?\$expand=Sensor,ObservedProperty	This API is used for getting all Datastreams for the Thing that has been chosen in the previous dropdown list. Sensor and Observed Property entities info are also being fetched in order to populate the second dropdown list
	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/Datastreams(283)/Observations?\$expand=FeatureOfInterest	This API is used for getting all observations along with their coordinates (through the FeatureOfInterest entity) that are associated with the given Datastream (selected in the previous dropdown list)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Observations filtered by given Observed Phenomena 	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/ObservedProperties	This API is used for getting all available Observed Properties in order to populate the first dropdown list
	http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/ObservedProperties(2)/Datastreams?\$expand=Observations(\$expand=FeatureOfInterest)&\$top=1&\$count=true	Based on the previously selected Observed Property, this API fetches the associated Datastreams along with their observations linked location coordinates. Pagination is being used for this API for improving performance.

8.2 SCENT Campaign Dashboard

The SCENT Campaign Dashboard aims at visualising and studying data related to images (photos) taken during the field campaigns as well as to their annotations provided by both users of SCENT Explore application (volunteers participating in citizen science campaigns) as well as the SCENT Intelligence Engine (employing automated methods to classify and annotate images). The data are obtained from the Harmonisation Platform back-end and the dashboard has been designed to visualise all the campaigns that have been performed during SCENT duration both in Danube Delta and Kifisos. The dashboard is user friendly and targets both general audience that can navigate across SCENT campaign paths and observe the related photos taken, as well as experts that can study campaign data in order, for example:

- a) to evaluate the success of citizen-science field campaigns;
- b) to compare campaigns' activity along time, to study the differences in the land scape and LC/LU across the different time-frames that the campaigns have taken place;
- c) to study the spatial distribution of SCENT taxonomy annotations;
- d) to get a thorough view of the areas covered during campaigns, not only based on the paths followed but also based on the spatial activity of the volunteers and the corresponding distribution of photos on the map.

The dashboard interface enables the temporal-spatial representation of the campaign data offering the following features (more details regarding the Campaign Dashboard functionalities along with the screenshots are provided in next chapter):

- Data exploration in both satellite as well as street map;
- Full and straightforwardly obtained information overview of each single photo taken including the image, the exact position on the map, the time-date information as well as all relevant SCENT taxonomy annotations provided both by the volunteer through SCENT Explore, SCENT Intelligence Engine (SIE) and/or SCENT Collaborate;
- Advanced filtering capabilities allowing to focus a) on data placed on certain locations or areas, b) on data taken within specified time frames, c) on data/images related to specific annotations or group of annotations, and d) on data/images associated with specific campaigns;
- Heat-map like representation of the annotation distribution across the map;
- Campaign activity monitoring across time including participating volunteers and photos taken;
- Clear KPI panel for fast overview of activity.

8.2.1 Implementation details

The Campaign Dashboard has been implemented in Tableau public¹⁹ and embedded in the Harmonisation platform website (<http://scent-harm.iccs.gr/>). The satellite map used is the free tier of Mapbox²⁰. The dashboard is fully interactive allowing on-the-fly data exploration and drilling according the latest trends of visual analytics.

¹⁹ <https://public.tableau.com/en-us/s/>

²⁰ <https://www.mapbox.com/>

8.2.2 Functionalities

The campaign dashboard comprises 7 panels, each one of them focusing on different aspects of the data. All panels are fully interconnected and a filtering action in any of them is inherited across all the rest of the panels. An overview of the dashboard panels is shown in Figure 28. A detailed description of all panels is provided below.

Pilot selection panel & guide: It allows the selection of the Danube Delta pilot or the Kifisos Pilot. Moreover, there is an option for a handy usage guide which can be shown in Figure 29.

Figure 28 Campaign Dashboard Overview

Figure 29 Campaign Dashboard User Guide (cheat sheet)

Filtering & Control Panel: This panel allows the focus of the visualization and analysis in custom time frames. Moreover, allows the selection of different types of maps that are observed in the Spatial Activity Panel, namely satellite map, street map, as well as a heat map visualization (see also discussion on Spatial Activity Panel). Furthermore, in the Land Cover Land Use drop down menu, subsets of SCENT taxonomy can be chosen for analysis and in the label source one can focus on labels provided by the different annotation channels (SCENT Explore, SIE or SCENT Collaborate).

KPI panel: It provides a number of aggregated indices such as number of volunteers, number of images taken per volunteer, mean value of annotations provided per volunteer, total number of images taken, total number of annotations provided by the volunteers (through SCENT Explore) and number of annotations automatically provided by SIE. The KPI panel automatically updates its figures depending on the active number of selected/filtered images.

Spatial Activity Panel: It depicts the map (either satellite or street map) together with all the geolocated images taken during each one of the campaigns. The images are illustrated as dots with different colour per campaign. The user can select with the mouse a subset of images/dots forcing all the rest of the dashboard to focus and re-compute KPIs focusing on the selected images only. Moreover, in the spatial Activity Panel legend, one can directly click and select among the available campaigns. As an extra functionality, when the user hovers over a dot, then the corresponding image is projected in the photo preview panel and a tooltip also appears shown useful information including the annotations that correspond to the specific shot. An example of tooltip as well as the heatmap option of the Spatial Activity Panel (that can be chosen from the Filtering & control panel) is shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30 Heatmap and tooltip examples

Temporal Activity Panel: In this panel the activity along successive time-slots of each campaign day is presented in the form of histograms. The user can click on a specific campaign or select the data resulted from this day only and propagate this filter across the whole dashboard. Moreover, one can click on the histograms to focus on certain time slots.

Scent Taxonomy Aggregation Panel: In this panel a tree-map providing the percentage of appearance of each SCENT taxonomy item in the selected images is displayed. Moreover, the user

can click on a tree-map tile (or on multiple tiles) in order to easily filter out the rest of the annotations.

Photo Preview Panel: It enables the preview of the selected images.

9 GEOSS Portal & OGC-compliant services

9.1 Connecting citizen-science to GEOSS

Citizen Observatories constitute novel sources of environmental information that can complement and extend traditional in-situ and remote sensing data sources. In particular, during the last years there has been a rapid increase of citizen-generated knowledge that has been facilitated by the wider use of mobile devices and low-cost portable sensors. To enable their easy integration to existing models and systems as well as their utilisation in the context of new applications, citizen-science data should be easily discoverable, re-usable, accessible and available for future use.

The Global Earth Observation System of Systems²¹ (GEOSS) offers a single access point to Earth Observation data (GEOSS Portal), connecting users to various environmental monitoring systems around the world while promoting the use of common technical standards to support their utilisation. Establishing a connection with GEOSS, can elevate the value of citizen science communities and data from local to global scales, facilitating their utilisation from a wide variety of users. In addition, GEOSS provides a framework of established data managements principles and policies, guiding data providers to the specification of the necessary information so as to ensure that their resources are discoverable and accessible via the GEOSS Portal. Further to this, the various citizen science initiatives and projects in place, have led to the creation of a rather fragmented landscape of repositories, having their resources available under different models, frameworks and technologies. Leveraging GEOSS and its data management principles can act as a deterring factor towards creating silos of resources, while promoting the use of open solutions and common standards for data sharing.

9.2 Process towards offering SCENT resources to GEOSS

In order to register the SCENT resources to GEOSS, close interaction with the GEO DAB team was established, following the relevant guidelines (Brokering Process). The goal was to achieve the following:

- To establish SCENT Citizen Observatory as a new GEOSS Provider
- To recognize a new set of datasets shared by SCENT project
- To recognize a new enterprise system, which will publish the new set of datasets (i.e. SCENT GeoServer)
- To recognize all SCENT interfaces (WFS/WMS) to be exposed by the new enterprise system (SCENT GeoServer)

²¹ <https://www.earthobservations.org/geoss.php>

In order to simplify the registration task, GEOSS has introduced two different registration phases, the Administrative registration and the Interoperability registration (and brokering). To this end, the new GEOSS Provider (SCENT project) and the GEO DAB (Discovery and Access Broker) cooperated and successfully completed the harvesting of SCENT resources from GEOSS production environment. The whole high-level process workflow that has been followed for the registration is depicted in the following figure.

Figure 31 Brokering process workflow for registering resources to GEOSS

More specifically, the following steps have been taken in the case of SCENT Project:

- **Administrative Registration.** This high-level registration dealt with the Provider Organisation (SCENT project) and its shared datasets. It was the first one to be accomplished. More specifically the administrative registration workflow consisted of the following steps:
 - Provision of a set of administrative information to the DAB team (Appendix A4).
 - The DAB team validated the completeness and format of the received information and stored it in the GEOSS registry (GEOSS Yellow Pages).
 - Notification received from the DAB team regarding the successful administrative registration.

Thus, by searching the GEOSS Yellow Pages for SCENT project, details can be found about its scope, geographic coverage and key activities, the Data Management Principles in place for

the data provided, as well as the Sustainable Developments Goals and the Societal Benefit Areas that the project aims to contribute to.

- **Interoperability Registration and Brokering workflow.** This was the second phase and consisted of the following steps:
 - Technological Information was provided to the DAB team. More specifically the SCENT GeoServer URL, the endpoints of the SCENT WFS & WMS services were sent to the DAB team along with the accompanied descriptions. In addition, information was provided about WFS and WMS services versions, the supported relevant operations through the APIs (e.g. GetCapabilities, DescribeFeatureType, GetFeature, etc.), the various feature types, the SCENT data to be integrated to GEOSS (i.e. event, images, video metadata) and the associated geographic regions that they cover (i.e. Kifisos river basin, Attica Greece and Danube Delta, Romania).
 - DAB team conducted a set of interoperability tests with SCENT GeoServer WFS and WMS services, including discoverability, accessibility and visualisation use cases. A test report (GEO DAB/SCENT GeoServer Brokering Test Report) was generated as an output of this process.
 - Notification was received from DAB team regarding the successful conduction of the tests and that no interoperability issue was found. Taking into consideration also suggestions indicated in the test report, metadata information of the datasets provided was further enriched.
 - As a final step of the process, the DAB team proceeded with the successful integration of SCENT GeoServer into GEOSS Portal (offering its services to production environment). Thus, users can access SCENT resources via the GEOSS Portal catalogue (<https://www.geoportal.org/?f:sources=wfscentID%2CwmsSCENTID>) as presented in the following figure.

Figure 32 Scent resources available in GEOSS Portal

9.3 OGC product certification for the SensorThings API

The OGC Compliance Program provides the resources, procedures, and policies for improving software implementations’ compliance with OGC standards. The Compliance Program provides an online free testing facility, a process for certification and branding of compliant products, and coordination of a vibrant community that develops and supports test scripts.

The purpose of the OGC Compliance Program is to increase system interoperability while reducing technology risks. Vendors gain confidence that they are providing a product compliant with OGC standards, which will be easier to integrate and easier to market. Buyers gain confidence that a compliant product will work with another compliant product based on the same OGC standard, regardless of which company developed the product.

The process of gaining an OGC product certification is straightforward. To begin with, an account was created for the online test suite²² and the implementation of the SensorThings API available at <http://147.102.5.101:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/> was tested. The implementation successfully passed all 22 test available for the three conformance levels. The test results are available at Appendix A5. Next, an account was created for the product registration²³ and linked to the online test suite. The product was validated as compliant implementation of the SensorThings API standard. Information about the certified product is available online, at the OGC Implementing/Compliant Product catalog²⁴, the product has received its own certification badge as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33 SensorThings API certification badge

²² <http://cite.opengeospatial.org/teamengine/>

²³ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/resource/products/registration>

²⁴ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/resource/products/details/?pid=1554>

10 Conclusions & Recommendations

Scen Harmonisation platform has been implemented according to user requirements, enabling the management, storage and provision of citizen generated, in-situ and added value products that are made available in the context of the project in an interoperable way. In addition, it provides the necessary interface to enable the abovementioned resources to be efficiently published in GEOSS portal as well as to be easily consumed and integrated into new models and applications.

Following the implementation of Harmonisation platform, possibilities that could shape the way ahead as well as recommendations (best practices) that would facilitate the conduction of similar activities have been identified and summarised as follows:

1. The design of a modular architecture that can store, provision and visualize data from heterogeneous sources in a unified way is crucial to the sustainability and maintenance of citizen empowered projects.
2. Ensuring the scalability of the persistence storage, in an easy to implement way, simply with the addition of clusters ensures the overall scalability of the Harmonisation platform.
3. In terms of the data quality, the employment of statistical methods such as the K-Means clustering method, provides a good approach on separating crowd-sourced data based to their spatial distribution as well as on identifying dissimilarities on the collected measurements. If this clustering is applied to both the spatial and temporal dimensions of the data, it can help cluster data into groups that were collected at nearby places and in the same time interval.
4. Facilitating quick and user-friendly visualisation and inspection of the citizen-generated and in-situ observations both in relation to time and space is essential. Providing automated ways and simple interfaces for low-level interaction with database layer can further support the integration of new resources that will be made available in an interoperable way.
5. Establishing a connection between citizen science and GEOSS is a beneficial process as it enables the uptake of resources in global scales. New standards such as the OGC SensorThings API should be also considered by the GEO DAB, so as to further enable harmonised access to resources via the GEOSS platform.
6. Considering the rapidly increasing volume of citizen-science projects and initiatives as well as the complexity of the interaction with GEO DAB, an organisational and technical infrastructure should be employed so as to support both the communication with the various repositories as well the connection to GEOSS.

References

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Appendices

1. The k-means clustering algorithm

The K-means clustering algorithm (a.k.a. Lloyd's algorithm) partitions a dataset into K groups, called clusters. Given a dataset of the form:

$$(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N), \quad \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$$

it must generate a set of K sets (with $K \lll N$), the:

$$S = \{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_K\}$$

which are characterized by which of the data \mathbf{x}_i belong to each set/cluster and the center of each cluster (a.k.a centroid) $\mathbf{v}_j \in \mathbb{R}^p, j = 1, 2, \dots, K$ which are the centers of the corresponding data \mathbf{x}_i of each cluster. In order for the clustering to succeed, the sum of the distances between each center \mathbf{v}_j and the data belonging to this set S_j has to be minimized :

$$J_{KMC} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in S_j} \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{v}_j\|^2$$

Using the membership function:

$$\mu_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{x}_i \in S_j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{v}_j\| = \min_{l=1, \dots, k} \{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{v}_l\|\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

the objective function J_{KMC} can be written as :

$$J_{KMC} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K \mu_{ij} \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{v}_j\|^2$$

the minimization of which can be achieved while the center of each centroid is defined as:

$$\mathbf{v}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \mu_{ij} \mathbf{x}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \mu_{ij}}$$

For the described clustering method, the following algorithm is used.

K-means clustering algorithm:

Step 1: Randomly choose the initial centroids $\mathbf{v}_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, K$ (they have to be chosen in the range of the data \mathbf{x}_i).

Step 2: Calculate the membership functions by the equation:

$$\mu_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{x}_i \in S_j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{v}_j\| = \min_{l=1, \dots, k} \{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{v}_l\|\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{and for each of the data } \mathbf{x}_i \text{ define}$$

the cluster that it belongs.

Repeat:

Step 3: Calculate new centroids as $\mathbf{v}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \mu_{ij} \mathbf{x}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \mu_{ij}}$.

Step 4: Calculate the new membership functions μ_{ij} and re-define the cluster that each data \mathbf{x}_i belongs . . .

Until the new centroids updated at the step 3 are similar to the previous ones.

2. SensorThings API, WADL

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<application xmlns="http://wadl.dev.java.net/2009/02">
  <doc xmlns:jersey="http://jersey.java.net/" jersey:generatedBy="Jersey: 2.17 2015-03-11
13:44:09"/>
  <doc xmlns:jersey="http://jersey.java.net/" jersey:hint="This is simplified WADL with
user and core resources only. To get full WADL with extended resources use the query
parameter detail. Link:
http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/application.wadl?detail=true"/>
  <grammars/>
  <resources base="http://147.102.5.93:8090/SensorThing/v1.0/">
    <resource path="">
      <method id="valueAll" name="GET">
        <response>
          <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
      </method>
    </resource>
```



```

<resource path="/CreateObservations">
  <method id="MultipleObservations" name="POST">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/">
  <resource path="/Sensors({ID})/Datastreams{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="sensor_datastream" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/Sensors({ID})">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="Sensor_update" name="PATCH">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/>
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="Sensor_update_put" name="PUT">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/>
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="Sensor_delete" name="DELETE">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
</resource>

```

```

<method id="sensorONE" name="GET">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </response>
</method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Sensors">
  <method id="sensorAll" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="Sensor" name="POST">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Sensors/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|metadata|\$ref}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="sensorAll_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Sensors({ID})/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|metadata}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="sensorONE_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Sensors({ID})/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|metadata}/\$value">

```

```

    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="sensorONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Datastreams({ID})/Sensor{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="datastream_sensor" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Datastreams({ID})/Observations{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="datastream_observations" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="Datastream_observation_post" name="POST">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Datastreams({ID})/{property_name:name|description|observationType|unitOfMeasur
ement|observedArea|phenomenonTime|resultTime}/$value">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>

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    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="datastream_property_name_value" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/Datastreams({ID})/ObservedProperty{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="datastream_observedProperty" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/Datastreams">
    <method id="Datastream" name="POST">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="datastreamAll" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/Datastreams({ID})/Thing{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="datastream_thing" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/Datastreams({ID})">

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    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="Datastream_update" name="PATCH">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/">
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="Datastream_update_put" name="PUT">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/">
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="Datastream_delete" name="DELETE">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/">
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="datastreamONE" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/Datastreams/{property_name:name|description|observationType|unitOfMeasurement|
observedArea|phenomenonTime|resultTime|}$ref}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="datastreamALL_property_name" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/Datastreams({ID})/{property_name:name|description|observationType|unitOfMeasur
ement|observedArea|phenomenonTime|resultTime}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>

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    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="datastream_property_name" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Things({ID})/Locations{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="thing_locationONE" name="POST">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="thing_location" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Things({ID})">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="Thing_update" name="PATCH">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="Thing_update_put" name="PUT">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
        </response>
    </method>

```

```

<method id="Thing_delete" name="DELETE">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="*/*/>
  </response>
</method>
<method id="thingONE" name="GET">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </response>
</method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Things">
  <method id="thingAll" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="Thing" name="POST">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Things/{property_name:name|description|properties|\$ref}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="thingAll_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Things({ID})/{property_name:name|description|properties}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="thingONE_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>

```



```

<resource
path="/Things({ID})/{property_name:description|properties}/$value">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="thingONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Things({ID})/Datastreams{path:.*}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <method id="things_datastream" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="Things({ID})/HistoricalLocations{path:.*}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <method id="things_historicallocation" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations({ID})/{property_name:time}/$value">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="historicalLocationONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations({ID})/Thing{path:.*}">

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```

    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="historicallocation_thing" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations({ID})/Locations{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="historicallocation_location" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations({ID})">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="HistoricalLocation_update" name="PATCH">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="HistoricalLocation_update_put" name="PUT">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="HistoricalLocation_delete" name="DELETE">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="historicalLocationONE" name="GET">

```

```

    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations">
  <method id="historicalLocationAll" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="ObservedProperty" name="POST">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations/{property_name:time|\$ref}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="historicalLocationAll_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/HistoricalLocations({ID})/{property_name:time}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="historicalLocationONE_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Locations({ID})">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <method id="Location_update" name="PATCH">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>

```



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</request>
<response>
  <representation mediaType="*/*/>
</response>
</method>
<method id="Location_update_put" name="PUT">
  <request>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </request>
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="*/*/>
  </response>
</method>
<method id="Location_delete" name="DELETE">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="*/*/>
  </response>
</method>
<method id="locationONE" name="GET">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </response>
</method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Locations">
  <method id="locationAll" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="Location" name="POST">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Locations/{property_name:description|encodingType|location|\$ref}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="locationAll_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>

```



```

    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Locations({ID})/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|location}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="locationONE_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/Locations({ID})/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|location}/$value">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="locationONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Locations({ID})/Things{path:.*}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <method id="location_thing" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Locations({ID})/HistoricalLocations{path:.*}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <method id="location_historicallocation" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>

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    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Observations">
  <method id="Observation" name="POST">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/">
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="ObservationsAll" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Observations({ID})">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <method id="Observation_update" name="PATCH">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/">
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="Observation_update_put" name="PUT">
    <request>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </request>
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/">
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="Observation_delete" name="DELETE">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="*/*/">
    </response>
  </method>
  <method id="ObservationONE" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>

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```

    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/Observations/{property_name:phenomenonTime|resultTime|result|resultQuality|valid
Time|parameters|{$ref} ">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="ObservationsAll_property_name" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/Observations({ ID })/{property_name:phenomenonTime|resultTime|result|resultQualit
y|validTime|parameters} ">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="ObservationONE_property_name" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/Observations({ ID })/Datastream{path:. *} ">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="observation_datastream" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/Observations({ ID })/{property_name:phenomenonTime|resultTime|result|resultQualit
y|validTime|parameters}/$value">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="ObservationONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
      <response>

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        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
</method>
</resource>
<resource path="/Observations({ID})/FeatureOfInterest{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="observation_feature" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/ObservedProperties({ID})">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="ObservedProperty_update" name="PATCH">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="ObservedProperty_update_put" name="PUT">
        <request>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </request>
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="ObservedProperty_delete" name="DELETE">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="*/*/>
        </response>
    </method>
    <method id="observedPropertyONE" name="GET">
        <response>
            <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
        </response>
    </method>
</resource>
<resource path="/ObservedProperties">

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```

<method id="observedPropertyAll" name="GET">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </response>
</method>
<method id="ObservedProperty" name="POST">
  <request>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </request>
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="*/*/>
  </response>
</method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/ObservedProperties/{property_name:name|description|definition|\$ref}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="observedPropertyAll_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/ObservedProperties({ID})/{property_name:name|description|definition}">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="observedPropertyONE_property_name" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>
<resource
path="/ObservedProperties({ID})/{property_name:name|description|definition}/\$value">
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
  <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
  <method id="observedPropertyONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
    <response>
      <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
    </response>
  </method>
</resource>

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```

    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/ObservedProperties({ID})/Datastreams{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="observedproperties_datastream" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/FeaturesOfInterest({ID})">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="FeatureofInterest_update" name="PATCH">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="FeatureofInterest_update_put" name="PUT">
      <request>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </request>
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="FeatureofInterest_delete" name="DELETE">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="*/*/"/>
      </response>
    </method>
    <method id="featureONE" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/FeaturesOfInterest/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|feature|\$ref}">

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```

    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="featureAll_property_name" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/FeaturesOfInterest({ ID })/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|feature }">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="featureONE_property_name" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource
path="/FeaturesOfInterest({ ID })/{property_name:name|description|encodingType|feature }/$
value">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"
name="property_name" style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <method id="featureONE_property_name_value" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/FeaturesOfInterest({ ID })/Observations{path:.*}">
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="path"
style="template" type="xs:string"/>
    <param xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema" name="ID"
style="template" type="xs:int"/>
    <method id="feature_observations" name="GET">
      <response>
        <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
      </response>
    </method>
  </resource>
  <resource path="/FeaturesOfInterest">
    <method id="FeatureofInterest" name="POST">

```

```

<request>
  <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
</request>
<response>
  <representation mediaType="*/*/>
</response>
</method>
<method id="featureAll" name="GET">
  <response>
    <representation mediaType="application/json"/>
  </response>
</method>
</resource>
</resource>
</resources>
</application>

```

3. Filter Operators and query functions

Operator	Description	Example
Comparison Operators		
eq	Equal	/ObservedProperties?\$filter=unitOfMeasurement/name eq 'degree Celsius'
ne	Not equal	/ObservedProperties?\$filter=unitOfMeasurement/name ne 'degree Celsius'
gt	Greater than	/Observations?\$filter=result gt 20.0
ge	Greater than or equal	/Observations?\$filter=result ge 20.0
lt	Less than	/Observations?\$filter=result lt 100
le	Less than or equal	/Observations?\$filter=result le 100
Logical Operators		
and	Logical and	/Observations?\$filter=result le 3.5 and FeatureOfInterest/id eq '1'
or	Logical or	/Observations?\$filter=result gt 20 or result le 3.5
not	Logical negation	/Things?\$filter=not startswith(description,'test')
Arithmetic Operators		
add	Addition	/Observations?\$filter=result add 5 gt 10
sub	Subtraction	/Observations?\$filter=result sub 5 gt 10
mul	Multiplication	/Observations?\$filter=result mul 2 gt 2000
div	Division	/Observations?\$filter=result div 2 gt 4
mod	Modulo	/Observations?\$filter=result mod 2 eq 0
Grouping Operators		
()	Precedence grouping	/Observations?\$filter=(result sub 5) gt 10

Function	Example
String Functions	
bool substringof(string p0, string p1)	substringof('Sensor Things',description)
bool endswith(string p0, string p1)	endswith(description,'Things')
bool startswith(string p0, string p1)	startswith(description,'Sensor')
int length(string p0)	length(description) eq 13
int indexof(string p0, string p1)	indexof(description,'Sensor') eq 1
string substring(string p0, int p1)	substring(description,1) eq 'ensor Things'
string tolower(string p0)	tolower(description) eq 'sensor things'
string toupper(string p0)	toupper(description) eq 'SENSOR THINGS'
string trim(string p0)	trim(description) eq 'Sensor Things'
string concat(string p0, string p1)	concat(concat(unitOfMeasurement/symbol,', '), unitOfMeasurement/name) eq 'degree, Celsius'
Date Functions	
int year	year(resultTime) eq 2015
int month	month(resultTime) eq 12
int day	day(resultTime) eq 8
int hour	hour(resultTime) eq 1
int minute	minute(resultTime) eq 0
int second	second(resultTime) eq 0
int fractionalseconds	second(resultTime) eq 0
int date	date(resultTime) ne date(validTime)
time	time(resultTime) le validTime
int totaloffsetminutes	totaloffsetminutes(resultTime) eq 60
now	resultTime ge now()
mindatetime	resultTime eq mindatetime()
maxdatetime	resultTime eq maxdatetime()
Math Functions	
round	round(result) eq 32
floor	floor(result) eq 32
ceiling	ceiling(result) eq 33
Geospatial Functions	
double geo.distance(Point p0, Point p1)	geo.distance(location, geography'POINT (30 10)')
double geo.length(LineString p0)	geo.length(geography'LINestring (30 10, 10 30, 40 40)')
bool geo.intersects(Point p0, Polygon p1)	geo.intersects(location, geography'POLYGON ((30 10, 10 20, 20 40, 40 40, 30 10))')
Spatial Relationship Functions	
bool st_equals	st_equals(location, geography'POINT (30 10)')
bool st_disjoint	st_disjoint(location, geography'POLYGON ((30 10, 10 20, 20 40, 40 40, 30 10))')
bool st_touches	st_touches(location, geography'LINestring (30 10, 10 30, 40 40)')

bool st_within	st_within(location, geography'POLYGON ((30 10, 10 20, 20 40, 40 40, 30 10))')
bool st_overlaps	st_overlaps(location, geography'POLYGON ((30 10, 10 20, 20 40, 40 40, 30 10))')
bool st_crosses	st_crosses(location, geography'LINESTRING (30 10, 10 30, 40 40)')
bool st_intersects	st_intersects(location, geography'LINESTRING (30 10, 10 30, 40 40)')
bool st_contains	st_contains(location, geography'POINT (30 10)')
bool st_relate	st_relate(location, geography'POLYGON ((30 10, 10 20, 20 40, 40 40, 30 10))', 'T*****')

4. GEOSS Resources Providers Yellow Page

Provider Name: Smart Toolbox for Engaging Citizens into a People-Centric Observation Web (<https://scent-project.eu/>)

Acronym: SCENT

Short description (summary of provider objectives and goals): Scent is a European Union research project funded under the Horizon 2020 programme. The project runs between 2016 and 2019 and comprises 10 partner organisations across 6 countries. Scent has created a toolbox of smart technologies and applications that aims to enable citizens to monitor Land Cover/Use (LC/LU) changes and how these affect flood phenomena in their urban or rural areas. Citizens simply use low-cost equipment to collect various environmental information, that are consolidated to improve flood modelling.

One of the key objectives of is to design, develop and implement a people-centric observation web that will be offered in the form of Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)-compliant resources to the GEOSS portal. These include different types of citizen-generated semantically annotated data (i.e. images, videos, text), sensor measurements as well as added-value information produced by the various Scent toolbox components (i.e. improved Land Cover / Land Use maps, flood extent maps, etc).

URL of the website institution: <https://scent-project.eu/>

Geographical coverage to the organization: Regional (Kifisos river basin, Attica, Greece / Danube Delta, Romania), National, Local

GEO affiliation: Non GEO

Name of official focal point: Angelos Amditis | Athanasia Tsertou | Valantis Tsiakos

Email of official focal point a.amditis@iccs.gr | atsertou@iccs.gr | valantis.tsiakos@iccs.gr

Name of technical focal point: Maria Krommyda | Nikos Tousert

Email of technical focal point: maria.krommyda@iccs.gr | nikos.tousert@iccs.gr

Type of online resource: Data (including imagery)

Type of Knowledge Body: None

Data accessibility: yes, without restrictions

Data policy: GEOSS Data Core

GEOSS Data Management Principles label: Discoverable, Accessible, Standard encoding, Well documented metadata, Preserved, Periodically verified, Reviewed and refreshed, Tagged with permanent id

Relevant SBA: Biodiversity and Ecosystem Sustainability, water resources management, disaster resilience, Sustainable Urban Development

Relevant SDG: industry innovation and infrastructure, climate action, life on land, good health and well-being, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Clean Water and Sanitation

Service endpoint:

<http://147.102.5.93:8080/geoserver/geomesa/wfs?service=WFS&version=1.1.0&request=GetFeature&typeName=geomesa:danubeImageMetadata>

Organisation Logo URL: <https://scent-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/scent-logo-web.png>

5. SensorThings API validation results

```

<log>
<starttest local-name="Main" prefix="tns" namespace-
uri="http://www.opengis.net/cite/sta10" type="Mandatory" defaultResult="1" path="s0004"
file="/srv/local/teamengine-te2/TE_BASE/work/srv_local_teamengine-
te2_TE_BASE_scripts_sta10_1.0_ctl_/sta10-suite/tns$Main.test">
<assertion>The test subject satisfies all applicable constraints.</assertion>
<params/>
</starttest>
<formresults id="d1e46_1">
<values><value key="level">3</value><value key="doc"></value><value
key="uri">http://147.102.5.101:8090/SensorThing/v1.0</value></values>
</formresults>
<message id="d1e187_1"><![CDATA[Test suite: sta10-1.2
===== Test groups =====
Conformance Level 1
  Passed: 6 | Failed: 0 | Skipped: 0
Conformance Level 2
  Passed: 8 | Failed: 0 | Skipped: 0
Conformance Level 3
  Passed: 8 | Failed: 0 | Skipped: 0
]]></message>
<endtest result="1"/>
</log>

```

See detailed test report in the `TE_BASE/users/maria.krommyda/s0004/html/` directory.

